

Coherent business model(s) and market entry preparation plan – Initial

D5.5

CiROCCO

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation
AQ	Air Quality
AQMN	Air Quality Monitoring Stations Network
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
B2G	Business to Government
C₆H₆	Benzene
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAL/VAL	Calibration and Validation
CCO	Chief Commercial Officer
CEE	Civil and Environmental Engineering
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
CH₄	Methane
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Development
CO	Carbon Monoxide
CO₂	Carbon Dioxide
COO	Chief Operating Officer
CPLD	Complex Programmable Logic Device
CS	Computer Science
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
CTO	Chief Technical Officer
CYS-CYSAB	Cyprus Organization for the Promotion of Quality
DAIRO	Data, AI and Robotics
DDS	Desert Dust Storms
DevOps	Development Operations
DLI	Department of Labour Inspection

DMP	Data Management Plan
DOD	Dust Optical Depth
EC	European Commission
EEZA	Estacion Experimental de Zonas Aridas
EFM	Environmental Fluid Mechanics
EMS	Emergency Management Service
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
EUSPA	European Union Agency for the Space Programme
EWS	Early Warning System
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GI	Geodynamics Institute
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
IAASARS	Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications and Remote Sensing
IBA	Important Birds Area
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IERSD	Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development
IoT	Internet of Things
IPA	Important Plant Area
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
IT	Information Technologies
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
LRT	Long Range Transport
MoU	Memorandum of understanding
NESSI	Networked European Software and Services Initiative
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NO	Nitrogen Monoxide
NO₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
NRWI	Non-Rainfall Water Inputs
O₃	Ozone
PICS	Pseudo Invariant Calibration Sites
PM	Particulate Matter
PV	Photovoltaics
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
R&D	Research & Development
RES	Renewable Energy Systems
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SGP	Sustainable Growth Programme
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SO₂	Sulphur Dioxide
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations

UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

H1 Goal/Objectives

This Deliverable D5.5 sets out the business principles and guidelines to be followed by the CiROCCO Consortium throughout the course of the Action and through the establishment of the CiROCCO alliance after the end of the project. It addresses joint and individual exploitation intentions, roles and responsibilities of Exploitation Champions, business objective and four business services and outlines the commercialization intentions that the entire consortium shall be aware of and comply with.

D5.5 describes the exploitation strategy of the consortium and individual partner organisations, market outlook and segmentation, Business models for the four business services offered along the instalment of CiROCCO system, outlines the administrative model for the post-project CiROCCO alliance joint venture and defines the elements of the roll-out strategy.

H2 Methodology

The fill-in templates and online surveys were designed to efficiently gather feedback from the partners followed by semi-structured interviews with pilot leader representatives, to ensure high quality of the outcomes and full compliance with the contractual obligations towards the European Commission (EC), as established in the CiROCCO Grant Agreement (GA) and the CiROCCO Consortium Agreement (CA). The definition of commercialization aspects and next steps considering the post-project Alliance ensure that the business CiROCCO objective can be pursued in the manner of best industry practice.

H3 Outcomes/Conclusions

This Deliverable is intended to serve as a guidance for the exploitation and commercialization activities of CiROCCO. Partners are strongly encouraged to review their exploitation intentions throughout the project duration and better define their role in the post/project business and technical cooperation agreements. Future work in Deliverable D5.2 and especially D5.6 will further elaborate on the initial plans and activities.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- CiROCCO business objective
- Individual and joint exploitation strategy
- Business models
- Market entry preparation plan
- Establishment of CiROCCO Alliance joint venture post-project

1. Introduction

1.1. Deliverable Description

The work described in this Deliverable is part of the work carried out in Work Package #5 (WP5) – Impact Maximisation and Outreach. More specifically, this Deliverable is the initial (A) version of CiROCCO Coherent business model(s) and market entry preparation plan, including templates and surveys describing individual exploitation intentions of the partners and their feedback on the commercialization of the project results.

1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable

This document describes the process of commercialization of CiROCCO project results. It aims to gather individual and joint exploitation intentions from partners and serve as a guidance for exploring the business opportunities. It presents the strategy, sets out individual and joint goals and gives an overview of the market dynamics, outlines the competition, defines the value proposition for the CiROCCO system and the four business services.

In more detail, the Deliverable 5.5 objectives are to:

- Define the joint and Individual exploitation strategy
- Provide an overview of the market and the market dynamics
- Shape the business models for the four business services
- Define the value proposition for the CiROCCO system and the business services
- Present a market entry preparation plan
- Outline the establishment of a post-project joint venture CiROCCO Alliance

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

1.3. Intended Audience

The plan set out in this document is both a shared vision among project partners in need of further refinement and internal review, as well as a presentation towards wider audiences, looking for strategic and consultancy partnerships. Following is a list of intended audience by target groups:

- CiROCCO consortium
- European Commission
- Earth Observation community
- Stakeholders interested in the uptake of the CiROCCO system

1.4. Deliverable Structure and its Relation with Other Work Packages / Deliverables

This Initial report is divided into seven Sections and six Annexes. A brief overview of the Deliverable structure is provided hereafter:

- ❖ **Section 1** is an introductory section of the document and provides a general overview of the Deliverable;
- ❖ **Section 2** presents the business objective and discusses the outputs for exploitation;
- ❖ **Section 3** presents an overview of the joint and individual exploitation intentions;
- ❖ **Section 4** gives an overview of the market and market dynamics;
- ❖ **Section 5** is a comprehensive presentation of the CiROCCO system and modular business services with business models accordingly developed for each service, it presents the strategy and the objectives, as well the post-project organisation in the CiROCCO Alliance and the commercialization activities thereafter.
- ❖ **Section 6** includes the roll-out strategy, gives a brief overview of further funding opportunities, outlines the risk aspects and provides mitigation measures and monitoring;
- ❖ **Section 7** gives concluding remarks and directions for further improvements;
- ❖ **Annex I** presents the summary of exploitation outputs regarding datasets;
- ❖ **Annex II** presents the fill-in individual exploitation intentions template;
- ❖ **Annex III** presents the CiROCCO Alliance draft Memorandum of Understanding
- ❖ **Annex IV** presents the business model canvass template
- ❖ **Annex V** presents the results of the online survey from the Stakeholders' workshop in Cyprus
- ❖ **Annex VI** presents the results of the online survey from the Stakeholders' workshop in Serbia

This deliverable is derived from the work delivered in other packages, namely the section on Individual and joint exploitation plans was originally written to accompany the Deliverable 5.1 Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan and activities. Pilot descriptions, functional requirements and KPIs were referenced from the work submitted under WP2 Interactive Definition of User-oriented requirements. In addition, the Stakeholders' Workshops organised under the Task 2.1 Stakeholder Mapping and End-user Needs Analysis through Processes of Co-creation were used to gather participants' feedback on the exploitation relevant questions and business model feedback. This Deliverable will be updated during the development of the Project and its Final version will be Deliverable D5.6 (to be submitted in M31).

2. Coherent business model(s) and market entry preparation plan

2.1. CiROCCO business objective

The goal is to develop an economically and technically sustainable sensor network, composed of a distributed, cost-effective electronic sensing node, having a direct impact on the current and future activities of research centres, industry and public authorities. Commercialisation services will be developed to financially leverage the value of the collected data and ensure the funding needed for sharing with the research community. They include the development of Renewable Energy Systems (RES) planning services, Health Air Quality early warning system, modelling of Greenhouse Gases (GHGs) and Particles Emissions and, Ecosystem Management services.

BO.1: To install and operate in-situ, low-cost, stand-alone, electronic sensing nodes in close collaboration with post project operating entities, having a real interest from local communities, including the commercial sector, offering a clear sustainability and commercialisation path beyond the project's duration.

In addition, the access to data is provided with multiple sources (e.g., within few minutes with satellite communication), allowing the development of additional business models. Data fusion services are provided through a Big Data platform (INTRA's Streamhandler Platform), further supporting the commercialisation path of the datasets and the expansion of the system to additional desert areas, as well as different hard-to-reach areas.

KPI BO1.1: To develop services on top of the collected data, promoting the interoperability and commercialisation of the datasets: ≥ 4 services to be developed.

KPI BO1.2: Development of additional business models during project implementation: >4 business models developed.

KPI BO1.3: To offer a clear sustainability plan allowing the expansion of the system after the project's implementation: a 5year sustainability plan to be produced and constantly updated during the project.

2.2. Outputs for Exploitation

The consortium partners have decided to take a multi-level approach towards managing the knowledge produced, where the respective knowledge producer holds the rights to the knowledge and shares the software and hardware implementation with the rest of the consortium.

The IPR management lies with the partner NOA responsible for maintaining an online document called Results Ownership List which describes in detail the level of partner engagement and the share of IP rights.

❖ CiROCCO Key Exploitable Results

The initial exploitation intentions towards the CiROCCO Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are presented in Table 1, which will be further refined and finalised during the project's duration.

Table 1: CiROCCO exploitation plan and timeline.

Type of publication	Owners	Type	Licencing	Time2market
Low-cost, standalone electronic sensing nodes	EBOS	Product	Commercial	2 year after project
Real-time access to data from hard-to-reach areas	ASTRO	Service	Commercial	1 year after project
Data fusion service between high- and low-end sensors	NOA	Service	Open/Commercial	1 year after project
Data fusion between EO and in-situ measurements	ICCS/NOA	Service	Open-source	6m after project
Big data services through StreamHandler platform	INTRA	Service	Commercial	3m after project
Renewable energy systems planning	NOA	Demonstrators	Open/Commercial	6m after project
Air quality early warning system for human health	UCY/NOA	Demonstrators	Open/Commercial	6m after project
Land use and ecosystem management	INO/VSUME	Demonstrators	Open/Commercial	6m after project
Modelling of GHGs and particles emissions	CSIC	Demonstrators	Open/Commercial	6m after project

All KERs are planned to reach TRL8 by the end of the project; this means that the consortium partners who will commercialise the KERs after the project's completion, require minimal effort, in terms of technical work for progressing the solution to TRL9 and offer it within Europe and beyond as a commercial offering. In this deliverable, four business plans are developed with products and services defined according to the predefined KERs.

❖ Datasets

Partners have submitted a preliminary list of datasets for exploitation during and after the project, some of which will be made publicly available through GEOSS. A more detailed summary including the management of all data will be presented in DMP. Initial overview, as presented in D5.1 is here presented in Annex 1: Datasets Exploitation summary. In order to support the culture of sharing the knowledge and contribute to the wider community, partners will make individual efforts to contribute to creating CiROCCO dissemination material, outlined in the table below.

❖ Dissemination materials

In order to support the culture of sharing the knowledge and contribute to the wider community, partners will make individual efforts to contribute to creating CiROCCO dissemination material, outlined in the Table 2 below. Partners have submitted a preliminary list of dissemination materials for exploitation during and after the project, some of which will be made publicly available on CiROCCO website and disseminated in other digital and printed media.

Table 2: Summary of dissemination material efforts by partners.

Type of publication	Partners efforts to contribute
Peer reviewed articles	ICCS, UCY, INTRA, EBOS, NOA (SOLEA, REACT, APCG)
Research assessment/study	UCY, INTRA, INO, EBOS
Poster	ICCS, UCY, INO, NOA (REACT)
Product brochures	NOA (SOLEA)
Blog posts	ICCS, UCY, INTRA, NOA (SOLEA), VSUME

Project brochures/leaflets	ICCS, UCY, INTRA, EBOS
Infographics	ICCS, INO
Other diss&comm material	ICCS, INO, MOL, EBOS, NOA (APCG), VSUME

❖ Publicly available e-Trainings/Courses

All online tutorials/trainings/courses prepared by the CiROCCO project through its capacity building activities will be made publicly available through the project's website and will be posted in a public service, i.e., presentations will be published in SlideShare, whereas videos will be available through the CiROCCO YouTube channel and on Google podcasts app. These will be all licensed via a Creative Commons license (likely "CC BY") to maximise reuse and share of the knowledge and target increased involvement.

3. Exploitation Strategy

There are five main aspects to CiROCCO Exploitation strategy: commercial, scientific, social, capacity enhancement and policy outreach. Each of these facets plays a role in successful advancement of the CiROCCO results. The commercial aspect focuses on the development of viable business models and commercialization opportunities. This involves identifying potential markets, establishing partnerships with relevant industries, and devising strategies to generate revenue from the project's outcomes. The scientific and technological aspect focuses on contribution to cutting-edge research and technological advancements. The social aspect involves understanding the impact of the CiROCCO project on society and stakeholders. It entails engaging with local communities, addressing social concerns, and promoting inclusivity and diversity throughout the project's lifespan. Capacity enhancement aims to strengthen the skills and expertise of the individuals involved in the CiROCCO project. This involves providing training opportunities, fostering knowledge sharing and building human resources to ensure the project's sustainability and long-term success. The policy outreach aspect focuses on engaging with policymakers, regulatory bodies, and governmental institutions. By advocating for supportive policies and regulations, CiROCCO aims to create an enabling environment for its activities and to align its goals with broader societal objectives. By integrating and effectively managing these five aspects, CiROCCO Exploitation strategy aims to maximize the positive impact of the project, foster innovation and drive meaningful change in the targeted domains.

❖ Commercialisation

Four cross sectoral business models will be developed aiming to showcase the sustainability of the developed system. CiROCCO will use the Business Model Canvas modelling tool to develop and select the appropriate business models, involving industrialists, research centres and users to ensure the sustainability of the systems developed, with the goal of incentivising, acquiring, and retaining profitable customers and subsequent commercial growth. A decrease of 60% the total price per monitoring station is expected. Through the strategic selection of the consortium members, which constitute a representative value chain of actors, encompassing academic and research technology organisations, along with complementary skills obtained from pioneer SMEs and public organisations CiROCCO will result in concrete and sustainable business plans adopted to the actual needs and outputs from the pilots. CiROCCO aims towards the development of cross sectorial business models that support the sustainability of the installed equipment and further development in additional desert regions in Europe. This is supported by the commercialisation of the equipment and most importantly by a series of data processing technologies.

❖ Scientific and Technological advancement

CiROCCO consortium partners are committed to use the Open Research Europe scholarly fully open-access publishing service for Horizon Europe to enable rapid publication times and publication outputs that support research integrity, reproducibility, transparency and enable open science practices. CiROCCO will develop a network of in-situ sensors, which will be able to gather information for variables like air temperature, sand temperature, humidity, solar radiation, etc. For direct integration and exploitation of the derived data, the consortium will ensure that the metadata will be compliant with ISO 19157, QualityML and follow the recommendations of IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change). This will result in the alignment and low effort integration with the current recommendations of the in-situ component of Copernicus, the GEOSS portal as well as ESA's guidelines. Moreover, the collected in-situ data will enhance the modelling and applications of other core Copernicus services, like the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (EMS), where the under-sampled desert areas are commonly affected by natural or manmade disasters and the lack of information leads to low quality products. Finally, considering the lack of in-situ data in deserts, the

strategic network of CiROCCO can also assist on the Scientific Calibration and Validation (CAL/VAL) plans of specific satellite missions like the Aeolus, or even enhance the information of the current pseudo invariant calibration sites (PICS). Active engagement of citizens will improve science literacy and build expertise among civil society, better access and understand scientific information.

❖ Social and environmental benefits

CiROCCO aims to increase the decision-making capacity for future missions and climate change priorities by providing data from unrepresented areas, mainly desert regions. The developed services will have a direct impact towards the Green Deal priorities towards Zero pollution. CiROCCO aims to increase the precision of developed models by 10% and offer dedicated services to tackle climate change adaptation and mitigation planning. Through co-design and participative engagement methods, the real-world needs of the users, their requirements and any limitations they may experience to feed into technology and service design will be identified, so that these and associated future business model(s) meet real needs of hard-to-reach areas.

❖ Capacity building

CiROCCO has a great and innovative technological and scientific work to be exploitable, but also has a social exploitation aspect of major importance. CiROCCO's pilots reach out to society as a whole, as one of the objectives is to provide capacity building actions to the pilot areas. Thus, by enhancing the skills, capabilities and knowledge of local key players (stakeholders, communities, authorities and decision-policy makers, researchers and citizens), sets the proper conditions to ensure the longevity of the solutions provided by the project even after its lifecycle. CiROCCO will train and educate local communities to increase awareness for the project, involve more stakeholders to collaborate towards sustainability while having the minimum environmental impact on the pilot areas. Proper communication and dissemination using every available channel will contribute to visibility, outreach and subsequently impact of the provided solutions.

❖ Policy outreach

The pilots and the project results act as powerful tools for policy support and decision-making instruments and authorities, to the benefit of the society in the local and wider scales. The exploitation of products is expected by the authorities responsible for climate change, environmental management and conditions, health and air quality issues.

3.1. Joint Exploitation Strategy

To orientate the outcomes from CiROCCO towards viable commercial solutions and assets, the consortium will adopt a focused commercialisation strategy with measurable outcomes by embedding commercial best practice into the project's lifecycle. Commercialisation will focus on delivering solutions that have a clear market opportunity that can be proven and validated through the pilots with key commercial stakeholders and in close collaboration with public authorities. The completed business models and marketing plan aim to outline viable and commercially relevant solutions, assets and services from the project by taking a broad cross-consortium perspective, with credibility built on a foundation of embracing industry best practice for bringing new products to market. With the objective of achieving sustainability, continuity, and eventually prepare the ground for market entry for the project's results, the consortium has drafted and agreed upon its initial exploitation intentions, as depicted in Figure 1. The plan consists of 3 phases:

Figure 1 CiROCCO exploitation plan and timeline

Phase I (M01-18) setting the necessary conditions for the business plan; Phase II (M19-36) that coins the exploitation, sustainability and go to market strategy, and Phase III (starting at the end of the project) featuring the sustainability plan for the uninterrupted operation of the system and the commercialisation roadmap.

3.2. Individual Partners Exploitation plans

The CiROCCO consortium comprises 12 organisations from 4 EU members, 1 Associated country and 2 non-EU associated countries that together form a complete group uniting the necessary expertise, skills, interdisciplinary knowledge and resources to constitute a representative value chain of actors capable of achieving the demanding project goals. The consortium is multidisciplinary, encompassing 5 major Academic and Research Technology Organisations, along with complementary skills obtained from 3 pioneer SMEs, 1 Industrial Partner and 3 Public Organisations to help achieve the ambitious goals of the CiROCCO project. Following are their individual exploitation plans, based on which further exploitation activities will be based. The template form is found at Annex 2: Individual Exploitation Plan Template.

3.2.1. Research Institutes and academic organisations

❖ ICCS

ICCS is a very experienced coordinating partner, with more than 80 successful projects coordination in H2020 and FP7. ICCS will ensure the strong coordination needed for such a big action involving a wide range of partners with different profiles and needs. It will lead the activities of the project regarding: (i) the system architecture design and technical specifications (ii) development of the algorithms running on the edge devices and the integration with the StreamHandler Platform, (iii) the technology validation and overall assessment of technologies as well as the replication guidelines. In addition, ICCS will handle the purchasing of all the equipment used in the sites ensuring the best possible prices of consumables and equipment. ICCS has experience in maintaining sensor networks gained from previous projects and ensure the post project sustainability of the installed equipment.

Table 3: ICCS Description.

ICCS	800+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
ICCS exploitation targets include the production of research results, knowledge dissemination and pursuing the potential of a spin-off company to exploit established experience in developed solutions (in-situ monitoring of under-sampled desert areas, sensor networks, data fusion between EO and in-situ measurements, etc.). The above goals may be achieved through collaborating with	

other RTOs, non-profit organisations but also industrial partners. This collaboration acts as an enabler for exploitation opportunities both at a scientific level and at an R&D level.

Expected Impact

CiROCCO will support exploitation opportunities at two different levels:

- (i) At a scientific level, it will acquire in depth knowledge with respect to in-situ monitoring of environmental parameters in under-sampled areas, as well as enhance visibility through collaborating with strategic industrial players of the consortium thus adding an application-oriented direction in its activities.
- (ii) At an R&D level, the gain of experience and increased reputation in the field of sensor networks and solutions development to enhance monitoring of environmental parameters in under-sampled desert areas through CiROCCO will enable successful participations of ICCS in future related R&D projects.

❖ NOA

NOA’s role in CiROCCO is four-fold: 1) Exploiting its radiation and energy expertise in developing solar atlas, nowcasting and forecasting, and its previous experience in Egypt with regards to dust and energy related collaborations, as well applications development (Solea), NOA will carry out solar related measurements and facilitate interaction with local partners. 2) Exploiting its weathered experience in in-situ measurements (APCG) and its state-of-the-art approach of scientifically fool-proofing low-cost networks for PM monitoring, NOA will be responsible for all QA/QC procedures of dust measurements across the pilots in close collaboration with the local partners. 3) NOA will handle the satellite remote sensing aspects regarding estimation of the dust optical depth (DOD) utilising the MIDAS and LIVAS in-house DOD datasets that will be also evaluated versus the low-cost sensors. Further, NOA will advance dust numerical simulations via data assimilation techniques in the pilot areas. 4) NOA will utilise its multi-faceted involvement in the GEO ecosystem to disseminate the project’s results and pursue linkages with ongoing GEO activities, especially in the in-situ, remote environments and climate change themes. In terms of exploitation intensions, NOA (through Solea) will pursue the extension of the existing collaboration with the Egyptian New and Renewable Energy Authority and the Ministry of Electricity and Renewable Energy as well as explore commercialisation of the produced technical developments. The scientific results are of great interest both for IERSD and IAASARS groups and will reinforce their expertise in Mediterranean aerosol science opening opportunities for further scientific exploitation and enhancement as partners in relevant R&D projects.

Table 4: NOA Description.

NOA	300+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>Basic research is at the forefront of NOA’s enduring scientific legacy; it is carried out by the three NOA institutes specializing in different scientific fields: (a) the Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications and Remote Sensing (IAASARS), specializing in the fields of astronomy, astrophysics, space science and remote sensing; (b) the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) specializing in the fields of air quality, environmental monitoring, meteorology, climate and climate change; and (c) the Geodynamic Institute (GI) specializing in physics of the Earth’s interior and Earth surface deformation monitoring using remote sensing methods, in seismology, geophysics, volcanology, satellite geodesy and marine seismology. In order to support both basic and applied research, NOA promotes consistently the development of innovative facilities in support of research activities carried out by all its institutes; it currently operates more than 550 land-based measurement stations covering the entire Greek territory, which are equipped with antennae and satellite signal receivers so that they can access numerous</p>	

satellites for acquiring high-fidelity data. IERSD/SOLEA deals inter alia with renewable energy sources (RES) research and development in terms of planning, management, exploitation and penetration into society. The RES market includes producers, electricity handling entities and decision makers. IERSD/APCG is involved in innovative technologies for air quality monitoring that rely on sensor technology. The relevant IERSD initiatives provide solutions in the framework of Atmospheric Sciences, Air Quality (AQ) Management, Exposure Science, and Citizen Science. The salient R&D focus that distinguishes IERSD in the field of sensor based AQ measurement is the rigorous calibration regimen followed for all operating and new sensor systems, which assures system reliability and data quality. Services are targeted at the academic/research sector, at public, regional and municipal Air Quality Management authorities, as well as at the private sector.

Expected Impact

- Strengthening and empowering the RES expertise of IERSD.
- Gaining more expertise in operation and calibration protocols for sensor based AQ systems in remote and challenging environments. Strengthening the position of NOA as a research partner specializing in sensor-based, Computer Science (CS) and IoT products.
- Utilization of the NOA brand for new networks with more/new public authorities & decision makers.
- Empowering in-situ EO in GEO.
- New experience in RES production monitoring and forecasting in under-sampled regions affected by dust sources and transport. Energy potential estimation improvement by assimilating the in-situ information into the modelling processing chain.
- Evaluation of the performance of PM sensors for dust measurements, for which data and applications are very sparse in the market. Accumulation of more experience in AQ QA/QC involving new IT approaches and training of new personnel. Capacity building to increase awareness, visibility and reach.
- Establishment of IERSD in the Egyptian region as a key player for RES planning and management optimization. Promotion of a reinforcement method for renewable energy potential estimation and operational production handling by calibrating on-the-fly the modelling output with the in-situ data.
- Expanding the portfolio of sensor calibration applications to dust particles, which is a key component of PM10 – one of the priority pollutants –, provides opportunities in Southern Europe and the Eastern Mediterranean, where PM10 and dust are a chief concern for public health and the climate, due to their proximity to deserted areas or as receptors of LRT dust transport.
- Market to remote, hard-to-reach- areas, new market segments

❖ CEDARE

CEDARE is an international inter-governmental non-profit organisation, accredited by the respective Arab and European Ministries of the Environment as well as the League of Arab States and the United Nations to conduct environmental and sustainable development studies and provide related services.

Table 5: CEDARE Description.

CEDARE	25+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>In the Arab region, environmental data is scattered between various organizations, regional and national research centres and statistical offices. The journey for data hunting is usually confusing, costly and time consuming. CEDARE’s Sustainable Growth Programme (SGP) addresses new and emerging concepts related to environment and development for human well-being, with a focus on</p>	

issues related to Sustainable Consumption and Production, Green Economy, and Green ICT. The Programme collaborates on global, regional and national efforts, addressing poverty alleviation, health, waste reduction (e-waste), green jobs, green ICT, pollution reduction, greenhouse gas emissions, sustainable consumption and production, and energy security. Together with its wide partner base from the international, regional and national community, the SGP implements projects, conducts research and studies, and provides training and knowledge dissemination.

Expected Impact

Through the CiROCCO project, CEDARE will conduct and coordinate the Egyptian pilot. CiROCCO will support exploitation opportunities at two different levels:

- (iii) At a policy level, focusing on the active contribution in the formation of energy related policies and the subsequent market uptake by setting up and disseminating a roadmap for implementations exploiting the synergy of Earth-Observations with ground-truth sensors.
- (iv) At an R&D level CEDARE will also use its network to provide valuable input regarding end-users’ needs, being involved in the co-design and co-development procedures of the project and provide input and feedback for the development of the CiROCCO system and services.

❖ UCY

UCY will conduct and coordinate the Cypriot pilot, focusing on the robust and accurate early warning dissemination system for DDS events, by undertaking the training of local personnel in the management and maintenance of the monitoring stations, as well as participate in the set-up of the early warning system, and will be involved in organising dissemination activities of the project results. UCY will also validate existing meteorological models for DDS forecasting with the availability of new data source.

Table 6: UCY Description.

Environmental Fluid Mechanics Laboratory - Isle of Excellence, University of Cyprus	1553 employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>The Environmental Fluid Mechanics (EFM) Laboratory, recognised as an Isle of Excellence, is a research laboratory of the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering (CEE) at the University of Cyprus (UCy). The EFM Lab facilities support both research projects and undergraduate teaching in Environmental Fluid Mechanics. The lab is equipped with a wide range of experimental arrangements for investigating fluid flow phenomena in environmental and industrial applications, such as urban air pollution dispersion, turbulence modelling, channel flows, buoyancy-driven flows and gravity currents, building ventilation, wind engineering, and coastal flows.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>The participation of the laboratory in the CiROCCO project will enhance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The capacity to attract or be involved in new European research projects related to the interaction between Desert Dust Storms and Climate Change, Human Health, Socioeconomic aspects. 2. Its collaboration and partnership network at European level. 3. Its access to or capacity to develop of novel and operational models and methodology for assessing the personal exposure to DDS and related health threats. 	

4. Gaining experience to provide consulting services to public bodies on DDS adaptation measures.

As part of the CiROCCO project, forecasting models for Desert Dust Storms are being improved, new data collection technologies are being used, and a comprehensive early warning system is being created. Access to these tools will enable the EFM lab group to provide consulting services to public bodies on DDS adaptation measures.

By implementing an early warning dissemination system that is tailored to local areas, more local authorities or government departments are likely to be interested in utilizing this know-how.

❖ CSIC

CSIC is Spain’s largest public research institution, attached to the Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness, and plays a key role in scientific and technological policy in Spain and worldwide.

Table 7: CSIC Description.

Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas	N/A
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>Through the EEZA research group, CSIC will leverage its 75 years+ of expertise in the biodiversity and desertification research in arid zones, by conduct and coordinate the Spanish pilot, focusing on the formation and transformation processes of spatial and temporal variability of biogenic and non-biogenic aerosol sources and sinks.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>Through monitoring parameters and variables to prepare local to global models of GHGs and particles emissions, CSIC will supervise the smooth operation of the project's sensors in two selected dryland sites and will contribute to the design of the project's contingency plans.</p> <p>From the exploitation side, CSIC expects to advance knowledge in the Mediterranean drylands in:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Vulnerability as hotspot of GHGs and particles emissions 2) Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄) fluxes 3) Atmospheric boundary layer and particle fluxes 4) Groundwater quality associated to atmospheric chemistry 	

3.2.2. Industrial Organisations and Small Medium Enterprises

❖ EBOS

EBOS technical role in the project, given its 18 years+ of expertise as a software powerhouse includes the acquisition of the pilot requirements and specifications from the pilot executors and translate those requirements into technical specifications of the technology to be developed within the project, as well as, to lead the pilots’ work package and specifically the scene set-up, benchmarking definition, operational management and DevOps task. EBOS will be responsible to develop the low-cost, in-situ electronic sensing nodes that will be used in the high-density sensor network aiming to enhance the in-situ measurement resolution in hard-to-reach areas. Apart from designing and maintaining the project’s website, EBOS will also leverage its wide experience in the market, to contribute to the elaboration of CiROCCO dissemination and sustainability plans and present project’s results to key associations through its membership (e.g., DAIRO, AIOTI, NESSI).

Table 8: EBOS Description.

eBOS Technologies Ltd	70+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and a short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>eBOS Technologies Ltd has more than 18 years of experience as a software powerhouse however, dedicated personnel within the company have more than 10 years of experience in the development of electronic sensing nodes. The company now operates in the FinTech & RegTech market for its software solution. Within the last 2 years, it expanded into the hardware electronics sector with multiple R&D projects, both internally and EU funded.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>EBOS plans to use the pre-existing version of the stand-alone, sensing system and the knowledge to design such systems to expand their activities by introducing themselves in the electronic testing and sensing equipment.</p> <p>CiROCCO project will support this strategic move of the company by allowing the further development and characterization of the system specifications. CiROCCO will test the system in real-life conditions providing valuable information for the evolution of the system to high quality and higher TRLs.</p> <p>The strategic decision of the company to move into this market will of course attract new and more customers from a completely different sector.</p>	

❖ INTRA

INTRA participates in the project as an experienced integrator of digital manufacturing and IoT systems, which a very strong track record of participation in tens of successful EC co-funded projects, as well as commercial deployments for manufacturing enterprises.

Table 9: INTRA Description.

Netcompany-Intrasoft	3200+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>Netcompany-Intrasoft (previously known as INTRASOFT International) was established in 1996 and quickly became a European leader in IT solutions and services with strong international presence. Its headquarters reside in Luxembourg and has development centres and operational branches in Greece at Athens, Thessaloniki, and Patras but also in Belgium, Romania, Denmark and further three countries. There are also offices in the USA, the UK, Cyprus, Bulgaria and the United Arab Emirates.</p> <p>Netcompany-Intrasoft has proven expertise in conceptual system architecture and system design, development of advanced enterprise microservices applications and CI/CD solutions, information portal management and project management. Emphasis is always put on developing applications that are modular, secure, and reliable and importantly, on offering innovative and added-value solutions that meet each customer's individual business needs.</p> <p>Not surprisingly, Netcompany-Intrasoft holds an outstanding record of +500 organisations (including EU institutions and agencies, national government organisations, public agencies, financial institutions, telecommunication organisations and private enterprises) in +70 countries worldwide having chosen and trust the company's solutions and services to fulfil their business needs.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>As of November 2021, Netcompany-Intrasoft is a member of the Netcompany Group, the fastest growing and most successful IT services company in the Nordics, owing technology experience and industry-specific knowledge. As part of the Netcompany Group, Netcompany-Intrasoft continues to</p>	

look for opportunities to capitalise on existing technical and business expertise and expand into new or adjacent sectors. By filtering industry trends and identifying emerging key enabling technologies, the company infiltrates its portfolio of products and solutions with these technologies to differentiate from the competition.

The participation of Netcompany-Intrasoft in the CiROCCO project is motivated by the possibility to showcase its cloud-based real-time data exchange platform and further develop Streamhandler’s capabilities for IoT applications.

Netcompany-Intrasoft is also interested in the commercial exploitation of Streamhandler by building applications for land use and environmental monitoring and attracting additional users from other industries.

Additionally, Netcompany-Intrasoft is interested in exploiting knowledge gained in further research activities other than those covered by the CiROCCO project and acquiring a competitive advantage by enhancing and underpinning the company’s position in Europe’s research and innovation ecosystem.

❖ INO

INO will lead exploitation activities in order to ensure the sustainability of system developed as well as be in charge of developing coherent business model(s) involving industrialists, research centres, and end users. INO will also contribute to development and deployment of the Serbian pilot activities, as well as be actively involved in communication and dissemination of the project activities, results and achievements.

Table 10: INO Description.

INOSENS	6 employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>InoSens is an innovation-driven boutique consultancy specialising in delivering innovative, scalable technology solutions and business services for diverse European value chains. InoSens is Serbia’s most successful SME in terms of the number of EU funded projects.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>INO will enlarge its know-how in the areas of commercialisation and business modelling for EO/in-situ monitoring applications and solutions at an EU level and will further develop its management and networking practices, allowing it to improve and expand its services portfolio.</p> <p>INO will coordinate the data acquisition, processing and analysis from the meteorological and air quality sensor network. The data will be used for short term (24h) drought and wildfire condition assessment, public health risk alert system (based on measured inhalable particulate matter, daily situation reports relevant for the area of southern Banat region and the Belgrade metropolitan area, with more than 1.5 million inhabitants). In parallel, INO will conduct ecological modelling based on EO products, field surveys of changes in land degradation and evaluation of the different risk factors. INO will also prepare studies of long-term ecological management, risk avoidance and mitigation planning.</p> <p>INO will capitalise on its strong existing position and business activities with strategic partners in this market, to improve its services portfolio and expand its contact base for the development of international collaborations, especially within the public sector.</p>	

❖ ASTRO

Founded in 2014, Astrocast is a leading global nanosatellite IoT network operator that offers a Cost-effective, Bidirectional and Comprehensive Satellite IoT Service to tackle global connectivity challenges in remote areas for industries such as Maritime, Agriculture & Livestock, Environmental & Utilities, Land Transport, Mining, Oil & Gas, and other IoT industrial applications. The Astrocast network enables companies to monitor, track, and communicate with remote assets from anywhere in the world, and is the only New Space IoT LEO network with commercial access to L-band through a strategic alliance with Thuraya. In partnership with Airbus, CEA/LETI and ESA, Astrocast developed the Astronode S, an ultra-low power and miniaturised module compatible with inexpensive L-band patch antennas. Astrocast is a public company listed on Euronext Growth Oslo.

Table 11: ASTRO Description.

ASTROCAST	35+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and a short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
ASTRO is a leading global nanosatellite IoT company based in Switzerland. Working toward completing 100 satellites constellation by 2024, ASTRO currently serves its customers globally with 10 nanosatellites and is planning to launch 10 more by the end of 2022.	
Expected Impact	
During the CiROCCO project, ASTRO will leverage its knowledge and equipment on satellite connectivity for IoT applications (low energy, short messages, small antenna size) to gather communication from any type of sensors or data logger in the field (remote area). By defining the data flow architecture, data formats, communication protocols and services, ASTRO will also develop the communication gateways to interconnect the wireless sensing nodes with the edge/cloud. From the exploitation side, ASTRO expects to advance knowledge and reinforce understanding in project's advances, extending the company's R&D activities.	

3.2.3. Public Organisations

❖ DIMOS

DIMOS will act supportively and as advisory body in the impact assessment process, as its feedback during the definition of the end-users needs, as well as during the Cypriot pilot execution, will provide valuable insights for enhancing the user-friendliness of the designed tools and the sustainability of project results. Also, DIMOS will widely use and promote the early warning dissemination system for DDS events, that will eventually positively impact its citizens and enrich its provided services.

Table 12: DIMOS Description.

Idalion Municipality	24 employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
DIMOS (named Idalion) is an independent municipality of Cyprus (public administration authority) that is located in the southern part of Nicosia province. It is the modern city of the ancient city (Kingdom) of Idalion that was founded by the hero of the Trojan war, Halkanora.	
The Municipality of Idalion is active in the field of providing services to its citizens. The main responsibilities of the Municipality are the construction, maintenance and lighting of the streets, the collection, disposal and processing of garbage, the protection and improvement of the environment and the good appearance of the Municipality, the construction, improvement and maintenance of parks and green spaces and the protection of Public Health. The Municipality via the Municipal Council is empowered to promote, depending on its financial capabilities, several other areas and activities such as the arts, education, sports and social services.	

The services of the Municipality of Idalion today consist of the following departments:

- **Office of the Mayor and Municipal Secretary.**
- **Secretariat-Archive:** This Department serves as the backbone for the Municipality. Assist Municipal Council.
- **Financial Department:** Payroll preparation, Payment of creditors and other expenses.
- **Cultural Service:** Organisation of cultural, artistic, social and other events of Municipality.
- **Health Service:** Conduction of health inspections of food preparation and distribution premises, sampling of drinking water from the Municipality's water supply system and from water tanks, inspections of swimming pools and control of their water quality, informing citizens about various matters of health interest, insects (e.g. mosquitoes and flies) and rodents control, cleanliness of the Municipality, investigation of complaints of sanitary importance, protection of the Environment and Public Health etc.
- **Technical Services:** Street/Road Network Planning, Zoning Studies, Complaints of a technical nature.
- **Employee Department:** Implementing the specified personnel administration policies and procedures.

Expected Impact

Within CiROCCO project Idalion will provide guidance and expert advice on the design and attributes of the DDS early warning system and will provide feedback throughout the development process. Also, Idalion will support the impact assessment process and will provide valuable insights for enhancing the user-friendliness of the designed tools and the sustainability of project results.

It is expected that the CiROCCO project results will help the Municipality to enhance its knowledge on the Environment and Municipal Health issues, focusing on the air quality.

In addition, the project will give the opportunity to the Municipality to promote the early warning dissemination system for DDS events, that will eventually positively impact its citizens and enrich its provided services. The results of the project will create a solid framework to strengthen the transformation of Idalion into a smart city, a fact that is currently a hot topic and priority of the municipal authority.

Development of a service through which the citizen will be informed about the air quality in the Municipality where he lives.

❖ MOL

MOL will actively contribute to the pilot in Cyprus and will provide consultation and input regarding the user experience, which will be integrated in the tools' development. MOL will also use the in-situ measurements to enrich its monitoring system and enhanced its provided services, while promoting the sound decision making in policy for the green transition and take into consideration the results regarding transferability to similar areas in Cyprus and public information regarding the air quality over the island.

Table 13: MOL Description.

Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance-MOL	922 employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
The Department of Labour Inspection (DLI) of the Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance (MOL) is the Competent Authority for the monitoring of various atmospheric pollutants, as well as for the	

assessment and management of air quality, in order to secure, as practically possible, the protection of the health and well-being of workers and citizens and the protection of the environment.

The aforementioned measurements are carried out using nine Stations, fully equipped with automatic real time instruments measuring the following pollutants: Nitric Oxide, Nitrogen Dioxide and Nitrogen Oxides (NO, NO₂ and NO_x), Ozone (O₃), Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂), Carbon Monoxide (CO), Suspended Particles (PM-Particulate Matter) (dust) and Benzene (C₆H₆). It is noted that, Air Quality Reference Laboratory, as well as the Air Quality Monitoring Stations Network (AQMN), are accredited by the Cyprus Organization for the Promotion of Quality (CYS-CYSAB) according to the Standard CYS EN ISO/IEC 17025:2017. In addition, the most important meteorological parameters are monitored such as Wind Direction, Wind Speed, Ambient Temperature, Relative Humidity, Atmospheric Pressure and Solar Radiation.

The results of the measurements as well as other relevant information are presented on-line, through the specialized website www.airquality.gov.cy. Since 2017 the Department of Labour Inspection operates a mobile phone application with the aim to directly inform the public, especially the vulnerable population groups, the employees and other interested people. Through this application, the visitor has access to the information for the air quality, in real time, based on the different colours of pollution levels on Cyprus map, as well as based on the concentrations of pollutants per station.

Expected Impact

- Air Quality Monitoring in small communities (Communities / Municipalities) using sensors in conjunction with Air Quality Monitoring Network measurements funded by the Municipalities themselves.
- Placement of screens in Municipalities / Communities to inform citizens on Air Quality in real time as well as other relevant information.
- Informing the Local Authorities / Citizens, by DLI-MOL Officers, with lectures / presentations on air quality issues and the main problems presented in Cyprus (dust / ozone).
- With the pilot study in the Municipality of Idalion (DIMOS) and the possible future application in other Municipalities and Communities, the measurements of the Air Quality Monitoring Network will be enriched at the local level but with less accurate measurements coming from sensors.

❖ VSUME

The Public Company for Forest Management “Vojvodinašume” is a private entity in charge of the management over protected area of Deliblato Sands Special Nature Reserve (35.000ha), where CiROCCO Pilot 3 will be located.

Table 14: VSUME Description.

Public company Vojvodinašume	1852+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>The Public Company for Forest Management “Vojvodinašume” is a private entity in charge of the management of the over protected area of Deliblato Sands Special Nature Reserve (35.000ha), where CiROCCO Pilot 3 will be located. The company is organised into three organisational levels:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Company Directorate 2) Sections of the Company- forest holdings and the sections of the Company “Vojvodinašume – Lovoturs” Novi Sad – Petrovaradin and „Vojvodinašume-Turist“ Petrovaradin. 	

3) Work units – forest administration and other work units.

The Company Directorate performs strategic, development and coordination activities and supervision of the work of sections of the Company. Organisational structure of the Directorate consists of sectors. Forest holdings are established on the level of forestland areas and their organisational structure consists of services. Forest administrations are basic units for planning and organisation of forest management activities. Apart from forest holdings such as: “Sremska Mitrovica” Sremska Mitrovica, “Sombor” Sombor, “Novi Sad” Novi Sad and “Banat” Pančevo, the Company also consists of the sections of the Company specialised in hunting and breeding game “Vojvodinašume – Lovoturs” Petrovaradin and „Vojvodinašume-Turist“ Travel Agency is a specialised agency, tour operator.

Public Company “Vojvodinašume” sells wood products mainly on the national market and minor part on international market.

Expected Impact

- During CiROCCO, VSUME will conduct and coordinate the Serbian pilot, focusing on the land, forest and protected habitat management and tourism development, supporting the pilot’s and project’s outreach activities, including setting all the necessary monitoring devices across the designated areas and engage with the relevant local end-users.
- VSUME will demonstrate the capabilities of the developed tools, aiming at indicating fragility to land degradation processes, assessing the impact of air pollution, monitoring the ecological balance and stability, and facilitate decision making to safeguard sensitive areas.
- Improved monitoring of the protected areas in terms of air quality and pollution levels might contribute to growth in tourist visits to Deliblato Sands. Experience of devices usability could/might be applicable to other areas (protected areas and forests out of protected areas) managed by Vojvodinašume, but final decision would be made after evaluation of effectiveness of CiROCCO project devices.

3.3. Strategy for the Management of Intellectual Property

In conformance with the rules for participation of current European Programs, a minimum set of basic principles concerning ownership of knowledge and access rights have been fixed and detailed with the signature of a Consortium Agreement (CA) before the start of the project, which regulates rights and obligations by all partners and will be further updated during the project execution. The IPR provisions distinguish between 2 basic types: • Background knowledge: Access rights necessary for the execution of the project will be granted on a royalty free basis. • Foreground knowledge: Intellectual property protection of foreground, i.e., the knowledge developed in the project and its applications will be filled, owned and funded by the partner(s) that developed the particular results. Each partner shall inform the Project Coordinator and the project partners 4 weeks in advance of the filing of a patent application. Subject to the provisions of the EU Grant Agreement and the CA any owner of any result shall be free to use such results and to move it to the market. In case of joint ownership, each owner shall be free to use such results in its own organisation but adhere to the CA and exploitation strategy with regards to commercialisation.

Relevant to knowledge management, CiROCCO employs the following strategy:

- ❖ Intra-Consortium Knowledge Management:

- 1) Technical and scientific progress: documents are placed in a document repository to ensure that every partner has access to them.
 - 2) Exploitation perspectives: INO has participated in discussions with the technical partners NOA, eBOS, ICCS and INTRA to help structure and map required knowledge and extra-knowledge needed to enhance exploitation (i.e., patents, technology transfer agreements, potential users, other projects) and propose an exploitation strategy.
- ❖ Extra-Consortium Knowledge Management:

Knowledge management will take place through dissemination to maximise the impact of the work done within the project. An online document exists for collecting and proposing to the consortium all matters referring to the results for dissemination and serves as well for monitoring the productivity of the project in terms of knowledge publications (scientific papers, posters, etc.).

4. Market Outlook

Earth Observation (EO) revenues for data and services are forecast to double, from roughly €2.8 billion to over €5.5 billion over the next decade, with the total revenues for EO data in 2021 accumulated to €536m across all segments¹. The market is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 7% from 2021 to 2030². The data from EUSPA EO and GNSS Market Report 2022 will be updated after the new report is published for 2023. The breakdown in terms of applications shows that EO-based climate-oriented services (modelling, monitoring, forecasting and climate change mitigation) hold by far the largest market share in the segment; revenues from the sale of both EO data and services in the Climate sector amounted to €318 million in 2021³. Astonishingly, the global remote sensing services market size is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 14.0% over the forecast period between 2023 and 2033 and according to the forecast, revenue generated by remote sensing system sales reached €16.8 billion in 2023⁴.

❖ Market Dynamics

The main drivers for this rise have been identified to be:

- i) Increasing adoption of renewable energy sources
- ii) Rising investments in several military and commercial satellite programs
- iii) Increasing integration of cloud computing in remote sensing; and
- iv) Increasing demand for EO data in climate modelling.

In terms of desert ecosystems, it is identified that more than 151 countries worldwide are affected directly by sand and dust storms, where only 45 of them are classified as source areas⁵. According to the UN Convention to Combat Desertification, 334 million people around the world, including 14% of the world's children are affected by sand and dust storms⁶. CiROCCO, through the additional geographical coverage with installed low-cost sensing nodes and provided services, could contribute beyond the traditional climate- and environmental-oriented services, also targeting businesses in the areas of Information Management, Disaster Risk Management, GIS and Mapping, Risk Identification and Assessment, as well as Capacity Development. Also, market expansion to other regions affected by sand and dust storms is foreseen, primarily Asia-Pacific, with just under 900 million people suffering from medium and high exposure to sand and dust storms⁷ and where the solar energy market growth rate is also reported highest globally⁸, with further exploitation plans including North America. Ideal locations for geographical expansion would be: the Oleshky Sands in Ukraine, Piscinas Dunes in Italy, the Bledow Desert in Poland, as well as the Sahara Desert, the Mojave Desert in California, the Tengger Desert in China and the Gobi Desert in Mongolia. Large cities around the world (more than 300,000 population) with very high dust concentrations would form a horizontal sub-target group for further elaboration of CiROCCO solutions to possibly engage other sand and dust storm vulnerable sectors, such as Transport (aviation & roads), Agriculture, Biodiversity Conservation and Public Health.

¹(EU Agency for the Space Programme, 2022)

² (Spherical insights - Global Satellite Earth Observation Market, 2022)

³ (Remote Sensing Services - Global Market Trajectory & Analytics. , 2021)t

⁴ (REP-GB-17920, 2023)

⁵ (Middleton & Utchang, 2017)

⁶ UN, Convention to Combat Desertification <https://www.unccd.int/land-and-life/sand-dust-storm/overview>

⁷ (APDIM, 2021)

⁸ www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/solar-energy-market

4.1. Market definition and segments

By understanding the market definition - the business or trade in a particular product, including financial products - we can elaborate on the potential of the project's system.

In order to understand the scale of the desired market, it is important to have a clear vision of the overall market scale. The European Union operates as a single market made up of 27 countries. The total value of all goods and services produced (gross domestic product or GDP) in the EU in 2021 was € 14.5 trillion⁹. The EUSPA presents an EO and GNSS global market generating over €200 billion of revenues in 2021 (with €199 billion attributed to GNSS) and predicts this number to increase to €500 billion over the upcoming ten years.

Globally, governments invest in space capabilities for governance purposes, to develop innovation and research capacity, and to address several socio-environmental motivations aligned with the SDGs and the European Green Deal. Investment in the space business and its activities have increased by 44% during the last decade, surpassing €75 billion in 2017, with public investments representing the bulk of the funding. Although private investment in space companies is minor compared to public funds, it achieved a record of €14.5 billion in 2021.

CiROCCO's market is positioned at the intersection of environmental monitoring, renewable energy planning and data assimilation services. The system targets regions characterized by challenging environmental conditions, specifically desert areas in Egypt, Serbia and Spain and following transport routes in urban areas specifically prone to dust storms such as in Cyprus. The primary beneficiaries of CiROCCO's services are governments, environmental agencies, renewable energy developers and industries operating in these regions. The market encompasses a broad spectrum of applications, ranging from sustainable energy planning to real-time air quality monitoring and ecosystem management.

CiROCCO's market can be segmented into several key categories based on the diverse applications and stakeholders involved.

4.1.1. Public sector

Collaborating with different regulatory entities from the public sector is focal in CiROCCO project for fostering sustainable development. At the national level, depending on the country, these are most typically the Ministry of Health, Agriculture, Environmental Protection, but also Labour and Social Insurance. The Ministries together with national environmental and health agencies, regional development agencies and similar government bodies comprise the most important – high level segment of the market. By engaging with key governmental representatives, CiROCCO seeks to provide valuable data for evidence-based policy formulation, enhance public health initiatives, optimize agricultural practices and contribute to overarching environmental protection goals in the targeted regions in Egypt, Serbia, Cyprus and Spain.

On the local level, these extend to local municipalities and secretariats with similar domains of governance, as well as tourist organisations and local communities. CiROCCO aims to improve the decision capacity of local authorities and support the health protection of the local citizens, achieved through the data assimilation of the developed dust transfer models. CiROCCO's services can contribute to public health by providing real-time meteorological data, such as air quality. The information can also assist in agriculture planning, ensuring sustainable land use practices and supporting environmental protection initiatives. Datasets will thus be made publicly available through

⁹ Facts and figures, EU economy | European Union. (n.d.). European Union. https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/key-facts-and-figures/economy_en

GEOSS. Public stakeholders will be asked to provide feedback during all activities of the pilots, as one of the end-users, and will be valuable for the correct design of the tools in this project.

Environmental Agencies, public enterprises managing land and forests, national research organisations are an important segment of the public market because of their role in monitoring and managing natural resources. CiROCCO's end-to-end sensing system can provide valuable data for these agencies to enhance their monitoring capabilities, enforce regulations and make informed environmental conservation and sustainability decisions. Government agencies involved in profit-generating activities, such as energy planning and resource management, can utilize CiROCCO's services to optimize their operations. For instance, the renewable energy systems planning service can assist in the development of profitable and sustainable energy projects.

Overall, academic and research institutions from various scientific domains can leverage CiROCCO's data for scientific studies, environmental research and educational purposes. In particular, the comprehensive dataset on greenhouse gases and particle emissions can contribute to a better understanding of climate change.

Both public organizations and NGOs engaged in community development, urban planning and environmental initiatives can benefit from CiROCCO's insights.

4.1.2. Private sector

According to the survey from researchers in the H2020 NextLand project regarding customer segments in EO, most companies (78.7%) focus on doing business exclusively Business-to-Business (B2B). Only 20% focused on both B2B and Business-to-Customer (B2C), a minority of companies concentrated on B2C (about 1.3%) and less than 1% (0.6%) concentrated exclusively on B2C¹⁰. The EO value chains are becoming global and numerous actors are entering the EO market, launching applications for the military, civilian and commercial purposes.

The focus of CiROCCO in the private sector will be on insurance and financial companies, users of meteorological data and data management platforms, data infrastructure/ data space operators, software vendors and developers of data platforms, SMEs and large enterprises from different industries, potential investors and funding organisations.

Insurance companies are global market players that rely on vast amounts of data for making accurate forecasts. These, in some segments, include meteorological data and increasingly cover the climate change associated risks. Although some of the banks that ventured early into weather-based contracts and invested into weather desks have in a course of a couple of years closed them off and thrown away the books, the re-insurance companies collaborate with international development banks as brokers for most diverse climate change adaptation schemes including weather index linked securities.

Users of data management platforms rely on efficient data management for their operations. CiROCCO's data management platform can benefit sectors such as renewable energy, environmental consulting and research, providing them with reliable and comprehensive datasets for decision-making and strategic planning.

Data infrastructure/data spaces operators' companies can leverage CiROCCO's capabilities to enhance and update their offerings. The project's advanced sensing system and data assimilation technologies can contribute to the improvement of existing data infrastructure, making it more robust and responsive to real-time environmental data.

¹⁰ (Lages, et al., 2023)

Software vendors and developers of data platforms can integrate CiROCCO's data into their systems. This collaboration could lead to the development of innovative applications and tools that leverage the high-quality environmental and renewable energy data provided by CiROCCO.

SMEs across various industries, such as agriculture, energy and urban planning, can benefit from CiROCCO's services. The availability of accurate and up-to-date environmental data supports SMEs in optimizing their operations, reducing environmental impact, and complying with sustainability standards.

Large enterprises can similarly utilize CiROCCO's ecosystem management insights, most importantly from renewable energy sector, agriculture and food production and processing, as well as manufacturing and transportation. CiROCCO results help industries optimize their resource utilization, reduce environmental monitoring costs and align their operations with sustainability goals, making them more competitive.

Investors interested in environmental monitoring, renewable energy and data-driven technologies may find CiROCCO an attractive investment opportunity. The project's potential to provide valuable data for sustainable development and its alignment with global goals like the SDGs and the European Green Deal make it an appealing prospect for funding organizations seeking impactful initiatives.

4.1.3. Representative country profiles

- Egypt

“Egypt possesses extraordinary solar resources that can be applied to a vast variety of solar energy systems and industries, including photovoltaic (PV) or concentrated solar power (CSP) plant establishments. Egypt has a solar energy potential of 74 billion MWh per year, according to the Global Solar Atlas¹¹. The country spans across vast desert areas, making it a very attractive starting point for expansion across the African continent. Egypt’s Solar Atlas states that Egypt is considered a “sun belt” country with 2,000 to 3,000 kWh/m²/year of direct solar radiation. The sun shines 9-11 hours a day from north to south, with few cloudy days¹². The poor economic standard and high exposure to climate risk comprise significant drawbacks for revenue generation, but the fact that NOA has already an established presence and collaboration with the local partners, as well as that CEDARE is an official institution with proven track record for business mediation and renewable energy investments in the region, make a strong case for a successful establishment of CiROCCO operations in Egypt.

- Cyprus

Cyprus and similar sites in the Eastern Mediterranean are in close proximity to desert areas in the south (Sahara) and east (Middle East), exposed to severe Desert Dust Storm (DDS) events characterized by high levels of fine and coarse particles and their adverse effects on human health. These DDS events have been found to be responsible for a significant percentage (10% - 40%) of air quality threshold exceedances on the island. Studies conducted in Cyprus and abroad have also demonstrated the adverse public health impacts of DDS events. In particular, early forecasting is hindered by the lack of in-situ stations to record the meteorological conditions and other soil characteristics (size, mineralogy, etc.) at the source, which are very important for DDS modelling¹³. It would be extremely beneficial if meteorological and soil conditions were taken into account during the development of DDS forecasting model as well as improving the accuracy of forecasts. Previous collaboration among partners UCY, MOL and DIMOS ensures a successful delivery of CiROCCO results

- Serbia

¹¹ (Moharram, Tarek, Gaber, & Bajoumi, 2022)

¹² <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/egypt-electricity-and-renewable-energy>

¹³ (Benedeti, et al., 2018)

The Deliblato Sands is a unique natural area of regional significance in Serbia. This area, spanning approximately 38,940 hectares, is the largest stretch of inland sandy terrain in Europe which serves as a habitat for numerous endemic species of flora and fauna, many of which are rare or endangered both in Europe and globally. The region is located near Belgrade, often cited as one of the most polluted cities in the world. The geographical area of South Banat, where the sands are located, is particularly vulnerable to pollution, including toxic gas emissions from nearby industrial activities. The combination of a Special Nature Reserve properties and urban and industrial pollution proximity creates a distinct opportunity for maximizing the benefits from installing CiROCCO system, crucial not only for its ecological conservation efforts but also for addressing the challenges of air pollution and fire risk management. VSUME, as the manager of the protected area, allows CiROCCO a unique opportunity to connect to the local stakeholders on the high level including the provincial government, national and regional research institutes and the local tourist offices among more than 40 institutions related to the area. Identifying similar areas in Europe and targeting the local key stakeholders in the same manner will prove a valuable strategy for new market penetration.

- Spain

Drylands cover over 40% of the Earth's surface and are highly adapted to climatic variability and water stress, but also extremely vulnerable to damaging human activities such as deforestation, overgrazing and unsustainable agricultural practices which cause land degradation, overexploitation of natural resources and emissions. A problem of the semiarid Spanish pilot area is facing is vulnerability of Mediterranean drylands as hotspot of GHGs exchanges and particles emissions. Densely enough spatial and temporal measures to cover this aim are needed. The goal covers local to global models of GHGs exchanges and particles emissions, including quantity (deposition rate) and quality (chemistry) of the particulate matter to discriminate near and far sources. The involvement of CSIC partners who already operates a set of experimental stations in the area is crucial for better understanding how the CiROCCO system will comply with the existing infrastructure and operating standards and provide a proof to the versatility and functionality of the system. CSIC is at the same time the key local stakeholder, gathering a force of public and private entities around the CiROCCO solution.

5. Business models

5.1. CiROCCO challenge and vision

The challenges posed by the deployment of CiROCCO merit careful consideration. First and foremost, disruptive advancements in environmental monitoring technologies may render existing technologies obsolete, creating potential business obstacles and challenges. This is compounded by the integration of multiple environmental monitoring technologies within CiROCCO, leading to a potential lack of awareness among policymakers, regulatory bodies and specialists about the entirety of its capabilities. The multi-input approach inherent in CiROCCO may encounter resistance from end-users.

Establishing the CiROCCO system and the formulation of policies for environmental and health protection may clash with prevailing human practices, necessitating modification or change. Despite CiROCCO's portrayal as a cheaper and intelligent solution, the introduction of novel approaches may make some end-users hesitant, particularly regarding the treatment of their data or operations using these new methodologies.

CiROCCO's vision is to establish an end-to-end sensing system, composed of a distributed network of cost-effective sensing nodes coupled with state-of-the-art data fusion remote sensing and assimilation modelling techniques. The defined network of sensors will enhance the current lack of ground observation in desert areas offering an operational and in parallel easy-to-maintain and -expand solution. Commercialisation services will ensure the installation's sustainability and simultaneously the FAIR management of data will support Cross-COPERNICUS ecosystem integration and assimilation services.

5.2. CiROCCO products and services

CiROCCO aims to deploy, test, validate and operationalize an end-to-end sensor network, composed of a distributed network of portable and cost-effective meteorological/weather stations and sensors in three hard-to-reach areas. The CiROCCO system will demonstrate how an extended network infrastructure (supplemented by LoRaWAN and satellite comms) can be used to transmit data from sensors in hard-to-reach areas to the central monitoring system. The proposed solution offers operational and in parallel easy to easy-to-maintain technologies able to assist governmental bodies in their battle against climate change effects and extreme physical conditions.

Four services will be developed to validate the quality of the collected data and drive the sustainability and exploitation path of the overall system:

- ❖ Renewable energy systems planning
- ❖ Air quality early warning system for human health
- ❖ Land use and ecosystem management
- ❖ Modelling of GHGs and particles emissions

5.2.1. Renewable Energy Systems planning

The Egyptian pilot will take place at the Benban solar farm dealing with energy management and production planning optimisation, exploiting the sensors information combined with the modelling infrastructure. Thus,:

- ❖ the solar radiation measurements will be used for the harmonisation with the real power production, for data assimilation to solar energy models and for forecasting purposes,

- ❖ the wind speed and direction will be used for the dust forecasting and load estimation,
- ❖ the PM for comparison with the dust modelling and for air quality quantification aspects and
- ❖ the temperature and relative humidity for the solar panels' efficiency, operation optimum conditions and maintenance alerting.

Additionally, real power and energy productions will be used for validation of the observational and modelling approaches. The result will be a dedicated energy management system for the Benban solar project and also a more generalised model capable to be replicated and applied at any solar farm across Egypt and beyond.

The main CiROCCO feature needed in the pilot in Egypt is to configure solar radiation and meteorological measuring parameters. "CiROCCO sensing nodes would be able to measure solar radiation parameters for the harmonisation with the real power production, wind speed and direction for the dust forecasting and load estimation, PM and ozone for comparison with the dust modelling and for air quality quantification, air temperature and relative humidity for the solar panels efficiency, operation optimum conditions and maintenance alerting."¹⁴

Solar scattering has a dramatic impact on power production. "It has been discovered that temperature and humidity, combined with dust allocation and soiling effect, have a significant impact on the performance of PV modules. In addition, particularly in lonely places, the wind itself carries a lot of dust and sand particles. The situation gets worse when dust builds up in humid circumstances and produces tenacious, sticky mud on the PV cell, which lowers power output by up to 60–70%."¹⁵

Accordingly, the pilot specific KPIs are set to include the:

- ❖ **Application for end users** (entities & solar farms) - a dedicated platform or application for desert dust storms early warning system (for solar plants production support)
- ❖ >90% percentage difference in desert dust storm events forecasting and **effect on electricity production levels**.

Value proposition:

Renewable energy systems planning business service enables solar power plants to better predict the power generation. Installed sensor network provides data allowing better operational procedures and longer lifecycle of the installed equipment, with optimized maintenance costs and less risk of exposure. Ultimately, CiROCCO system allows for identification of different constituents which might affect or cause the scattering of the incoming solar radiation.

The main elements of a business service Renewable energy systems planning service are outlined in the Figure 2 below.

¹⁴ Reported by CEDARE for the needs of Task 2.2 Pilot Requirements and Specifications for Hard-to-reach Under-sampled Areas

¹⁵ (Shaik, Lingala, & Veeraboina, 2023)

Figure 2: Renewable energy systems planning service business model canvas.

5.2.2. 5.2.2. Air quality early warning system for human health

The region of Cyprus experiences frequent and sometimes severe Desert Dust Storm (DDS) events characterized by high levels of fine and coarse particles. These DDS events have been found to be responsible for a significant percentage (10% - 40%) of air quality threshold exceedances on the island¹⁶. Studies conducted in Cyprus and abroad have also demonstrated the adverse public health impacts of DDS events. Furthermore, a survey conducted among stakeholders in Cyprus and other Eastern Mediterranean countries revealed gaps in the implementation of pre-determined action plans for public protection during DDS events. This was emphasized during the First Stakeholders workshop in Cyprus by the representatives from the Ministry of Health and other concerned participants.

In Cyprus and similar regions of the Eastern Mediterranean, where the ability to implement limiting DDS is nearly non-existent, the only alternative is to adopt small-scale and individual adaptation measures. Specifically, the establishment of an early warning system for DDS is a primary strategy that may be taken to protect citizens from such harmful events. However, for the Eastern Mediterranean region which is near desert areas in the south (Sahara) and east (Middle East), early forecasting is hindered by the lack of in-situ stations to record the meteorological conditions and other soil characteristics (size, mineralogy, etc.) at the source, which are very important for DDS modelling. As a result, existing forecasting models often miss the intensity of DDS phenomena capable of significantly affecting air quality in urban environments.¹⁷

Effective dissemination of early warning information to the public and relevant stakeholders could pose significant challenges. In order to develop a user-friendly platform, such as a website or mobile application that is tailored to the individual needs of users, attention needs to be paid to the design, usability, and accessibility aspects. This is to ensure that a broad spectrum of end-users can not only access the information but also comprehend it easily and take appropriate action. Under Pilot 2, the efficacy of these platforms will be assessed against specific KPIs and targets. Firstly, it is anticipated that more than 500 unique users will engage with the dedicated platform, or the specialized application designed for the DDS early warning system. Secondly, by the culmination of the program, the system is projected to predict over 75% of DDS in the region in terms of their occurrence and intensity. This will provide valuable information about the accuracy and reliability of the monitoring system in providing early warnings.

Accordingly, the pilot specific KPIs are set to include the:

- ❖ **Early warning application for end users** (municipalities & public) - a dedicated application for desert dust storms early warning system (free mobile app for citizens)
- ❖ >75% percentage **desert dust storm events successfully forecasted** in terms of their occurrence and intensity.

Value proposition

Air quality Early Warning System for Human Health enables governments to provide reliable early warning about incoming DDS through an app based on real time and relevant measurements.

CiROCCO offers turn-key service - the research accompanying software and hardware installation, with full technical and customer support.

CiROCCO system is a modular and scalable solution to address particular needs of the affected region, and our consortium is carefully crafted to ensure R&D support for long term government projects.

¹⁶ (Achilleos, et al., 2020)

¹⁷ Reported by UCY for the needs of Task 2.2 Pilot Requirements and Specifications for Hard-to-reach Under-sampled Areas

The main elements of a business service Air quality early warning system for human health are outlined in the Figure 3 below.

The key takeaways from a structured interview with UCY is that there is an existing cooperation between the University and the municipality and the ongoing support to deliver the app to the citizens. An important aspect of this Business-to-Government (B2G) cooperation is in the fact that the app as the final product will be free for the citizens, therefore the business model is double layered service, providing scientific research and modelling together with app development to the municipality on one hand, and providing citizens with reliable data relevant to national health on the other.

During the Exploitation workshop on Day one of the General Assembly in Cyprus, the participants were asked to answer several questions about the proposed business service and help the consortium better understand the market needs and the value proposition. Some of the highlights are given below, with screenshot results in the Annex 5 Exploitation survey results Cyprus.

One of the first questions was related to the needs assessment “Which problems can the Air quality early warning system for human health solve, which needs are we addressing?” Keywords such as vulnerable groups, proactive health protection and early warning appeared, accompanied by a need for detection and definition of air pollution sources and pollutants most closely associated with health endpoints (e.g., mortality). Real time and reliable warnings were of importance to the audience.

Most of the participants were aware of similar early warning services and named governments as providers. Regarding the target regions for expansion, the presumably most affected by the DDS events in the next five years will be the Mediterranean, the Middle East and North Africa, which makes them the prime areas for looking into business to government modes of cooperation and expansion of CiROCCO services. Cairo was identified as the municipality with a large number of citizens exposed to desert dust storm events. Market penetration was seen as an important business risk to consider, given the nature of government contracts. Involving government representatives in the development of the product and nurturing a personalised relationship is further proposed as a mitigation measure.

Given the free service offered by the app, the issue of advertising revenue was raised during the workshop. INO suggested that in this kind of relationship, it would be logical that the government, i.e. municipality, harnesses the advertising revenue, which most often creates more problems for the administration that profit, so the business model foresees no adds placed through the app. Nevertheless, additional services that could be extended to citizens could be switched on or off for a compensation towards the developers, and some of the questions were testing the audience reaction to the amount of money they were willing to pay as well as the kind of service they would like to have in addition to the early warning. There was a slight preference for paying a 1-5 EUR monthly fee for additional weather forecasting services within the app, and while no one would pay above 15 EUR, slightly less than half participants would not pay at all. This is presumably because of already existing forecasting services available for free, yet the reliability of forecasts and potential longer forecasting horizons might be of relevance for further development after the initial product launch. Looking into ways for a more personalized approach and exploring the competition on the market, one company distinguished itself by offering chat options where one could ask a question directly to the meteorologist in a text message exchange. No respondents found this option appealing enough to pay for it. On the other hand, most of the participants were interested in additional features of the app such as data export, localisation support for languages and regions and to a minor extent in owning company shares.

The replicability of the system was assessed as Moderate – where CiROCCO system would need additional effort and funds to expand to other markets. The World Health Organisation Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean was suggested for a strategic and global partnership, while the insurance industry was recognized as the sector to go to for consultancy partnership.

Touching on the branding as well, the participants were asked to suggest a brand name for the app. DustIN, AirQ App and Dust EWS were some of the suggestions.

The survey was conducted as preliminary research to gather opinion and suggestions from the key stakeholders and will serve a guideline for a more detailed analysis of the user needs and market prospects to be employed during the market entry phase. A larger focus group would be needed to test the product value proposition and the pricing strategy in particular, but for the preliminary phase, the overall conclusions are positive and promising for the Early warning system business service.

Figure 3: Air quality early warning system for human health.

5.2.3. Land use and ecosystem management

Deliblato Sands is the largest inland sandy terrain in Europe (38.940 ha) 49, with some of the largest known dunes in the Carpathian basin, measuring up to 30 meters in relative height. Once part of a vast prehistoric desert, having originated from river sediments deposited by wind in cooler climatic phases in the last 2,5 million years, it is now home to many endemic species of plants and animals which are rare or endangered in Europe and globally. It is classified as a category IV of International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) classification – Habitat and Species Management Area. In addition, Deliblato sands is: Important Birds Area (IBA), Important Plant Area in Europe (IPA), Emerald Area, Ramsar Area (Labudovo okno, a part of the desert alongside the Danube) and potential UNESCO world heritage site. Specifically, the south Banat geographical area is exposed to strong winds assumed to be carrying pollutants such as toxic gas emissions from neighbouring thermal plant Kostolac and surrounding housing. Additionally, Deliblato sands is recognised as the most fire-prone area in the Republic of Serbia, with its combination of sandy soils with high water permeability and dry surface, warm and arid climate and easily flammable coniferous vegetation.

The data collected from the sensor network will be used to develop and implement new ecological management model. This model will assist in decision-making processes, like choosing suitable plant species for reforestation, better planning of conservation measures, and monitoring of microclimate changes. The aim is to enhance the sustainable management of land, forest, habitat, and tourism activities in the area.

Accordingly, the pilot specific KPIs are set to include the:

- ❖ **>30 Fire risk maps produced** (agency & public) - daily fire risk assessment
- ❖ **>3 Ecological model maps produced** - monthly environmental change maps.

Value proposition:

Land Use and Ecosystem Management Decision support system enables governing entities to perform near real time mapping of vegetation and land use. Installed sensor network provides datasets so far unavailable, allowing for optimization of internal procedures for fire management as well as optimized timing for reforestation action.

The main elements of a business service Land Use and Ecosystem Management Decision support system are outlined in the Figure 4 below.

During the Exploitation workshop in Serbia, the participants were asked to answer several questions about the proposed business service and help the consortium better understand the market needs and the value proposition. Some of the highlights are given below, with screenshot results in the Annex 6 Exploitation survey results Serbia.

One of the first questions was related to the needs assessment “Which problems can the Land use and ecosystem management solve, which needs are we addressing?” Answers such as ecosystem preservation, sustainable land management, fire management, air quality monitoring and decision-making support were pronounced.

The participants were split in half regarding the awareness of similar decision support systems and named governments and national services as providers, but more than half were aware of wildfire prevention support tool. The answers on the fire protection provider were also more specific, listing real-time maps of active fires on the national territory, internal surveillance systems as well as private market companies and Horizon 2020 project results. Market penetration was seen as an important

business risk to consider, given the nature of government contracts. Organising demo days was second to having political connections and close liaisons were proposed as a mitigation measure.

Of the four provided processes, the participants listed the following in order of importance to sustainable ecosystem management. Land use planning at decentralised and local levels was rated as the most important, Financing mechanism second, High-level policies third and Realistic budget allocation last. The most important benefits were Access to clean air and water first, Biodiversity preservation second, better nutrition and health third and Continuous provision of ecosystem goods last.

The majority of participants reported there is a large forest ecosystem in their area, and all of them stated they would like to participate in a more sustainable land management in their area. Looking into ways for a more personalized approach and exploring the competition on the market, one platform distinguished itself by offering to select the land, choose a sustainable practice offered and vote for implementation. Less than half of the respondents found the option to donate for such practices appealing, and strongly preferred the smaller amount of 50 EUR annually, compared to 200 or more annual donation. Presumably, the citizens traditionally rely on their tax money to go to the right purposes and be properly managed by the national authorities in charge of the ecosystem and land management. Nevertheless, given the high interest into personal wellbeing and raising ecological awareness, crowdsourcing may be a potential channel for securing funds for ecosystem and air quality oriented CiROCCO system implementation.

The replicability of the system was assessed almost equally as being High – where CiROCCO system can go global with the service and Moderate – where CiROCCO system would need additional effort and funds to expand to other markets.

The Serbian environmental Protection Agency was suggested for a strategic partnership, along with the relevant ministries and other national institutions. National research institutes as well as the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts were recommended for consultancy partnership. Several institutions were recommended as global partners including European Environment Agency, World Health Organization, National Aeronautics and Space Administration and the World Meteorological Organization.

Touching on the branding as well, the participants were asked to suggest a brand name for the service. LUEMDSS, Land and Ecomanagement were some of the suggestions.

The survey was conducted as preliminary research to gather opinion and suggestions from the key stakeholders and will serve a guideline for a more detailed analysis of the user needs and market prospects to be employed during the market entry phase. A larger focus group would be needed to test the product value proposition and the pricing strategy in particular, but for the preliminary phase, the overall conclusions are positive and promising for the Land use and ecosystem management.

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

Land Use and Ecosystem Management

Designed by:

INO

Date:

05/12/2023

Version:

1.0

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Governmental institutions: Ministries Municipalities of large cities exposed to land degradation, wildfire risk and air pollution Entities with similar ecosystem management services developed or without any Scientific institutions</p> <p>Private landowners: Citizens or private entities owning large forests or land in need of a better in-situ coverage</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Subscription fee + Leasing for the equipment with bundles for consulting days. Dynamic pricing - negotiating the service price specific to each customer, with the fixed part of the price depending on the product features and volume of data for storage and processing</p>				

Figure 4: Land Use and Ecosystem Management Decision support system.

5.2.4. Modelling of GHGs and particles emissions

Drylands cover over 40% of the Earth's surface and are highly adapted to climatic variability and water stress, but also extremely vulnerable to damaging human activities such as deforestation, overgrazing, unsustainable agricultural practices, which cause land degradation, overexploitation of natural resources, and emissions. A problem of the semiarid Spanish pilot is facing is vulnerability of Mediterranean drylands as hotspot of GHGs exchanges and particles emissions. Densely enough spatial and temporal measures to cover this aim are needed.¹⁸

Tabernas badlands in Almería constitute one of the most extensive badland landscapes in semi-arid south-east Spain and one of the driest areas in Europe.¹⁹ The main challenge that these specific areas are facing is the vulnerability of the Mediterranean drylands as a hotspot of GHGs exchanges and particles emissions, contaminating the non-rainfall water inputs (NRWI) and thus affecting the soil microbial activity and the plant productivity.²⁰ Installation of CiROCCO system contributes to following priorities 1) Vulnerability of Mediterranean drylands as hotspot of GHGs and particles emissions; 2) CO₂ subterranean ventilation from drylands; 3) Atmospheric boundary layer and particle fluxes from drylands; and 4) Groundwater quality associated to atmospheric chemistry in drylands. CiROCCO technology will contribute to improve the spatial prediction of the environmental variables through an integrated real-time system of measurements.

Accordingly, the pilot specific KPIs are set to include the

- ❖ **>4 Dust-induced Water Quality Assessment Maps produced** (institute & public) – monthly water quality assessment maps.

Value proposition

Modelling of GHGs and particles emissions enables governing entities to assess the vulnerability of the monitored region, contamination and quality of the air and groundwater. Installed sensor network provides datasets so far unavailable, allowing for measuring volume and chemistry of dust and monitoring air and water pollution.

The main elements of a business service Land Use and Ecosystem Management Decision support system are outlined in the Figure 5 below.

¹⁸ Reported by CSIC for the needs of Task 2.2 Pilot Requirements and Specifications for Hard-to-reach Under-sampled Areas

¹⁹ (Calvo-Cases, et al., 2014)

²⁰ (Chamizo, Rodríguez-Caballero, Moro, & Cantón, 2021)

Business Model Canvas

Designed for:

Modelling of GHGs and Particles Emissions

Designed by:

INO

Date:

09/12/2023

Version:

1.0

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Governmental institutions: Ministries Regional development agencies covering areas exposed to land degradation, greenhouse gasses and air pollution Entities with similar ecosystem management services developed or without any Scientific institutions</p> <p>Private landowners: Citizens or private entities owning large forests or land in need of a better in-situ coverage</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Subscription fee + Leasing for the equipment with bundles for consulting days. Dynamic pricing - negotiating the service price specific to each customer, with the fixed part of the price depending on the product features and volume of data for storage and processing</p>				

Figure 5: Modelling of GHGs and Particles Emissions.

5.3. Competition

Currently, there are numerous, commercially-available weather stations²¹ and low-cost sensing nodes²² covering the vast majority of the required parameters to monitor. However, most of these systems are designed for dedicated applications²³ and they are separated into two main categories; the high-quality, high cost (tenths of thousands of Euros) and the low-cost (hundreds of Euros), low-quality systems^{24, 25}. Furthermore, the existing systems although they can measure most of the required parameters are not designed for desert environments²⁶. Deserts and generally high dust concentration environments are extremely harsh and necessitate proper packaging in order to extend the system's lifetime as well as ensuring the accuracy of the measurements in such wide range of temperatures (-5°C - 40°C)²⁷ between day and night.

Most sensing systems available for such environments are bulky and of high cost, which prohibits their use in high-density sensor networks. In order to enhance the spatial and time density of the measurements, low-cost, miniaturised and well-protected sensing nodes are required. There are currently miniaturised sensors for the required parameters and several electronic systems to go along with them but they are scattered and fragmented. **An integrated, stand-alone sensing system capable of surviving the harsh desert environment, with adequate lifetimes, monitoring the right parameters and at low-cost is completely missing.**

Another crucial limitation that desert areas face is the high acquisition time to get the data from these remote areas. The aforementioned can have a major impact on the type of services that can be developed. Cellular networks can be exploited for providing network coverage to hard-to-reach areas; however, one major limitation is still the cost of backhaul deployment and the related energy consumption. It is yet to be studied how different communication technologies as well as edge processing solutions can be combined, in a holistic and operational approach, considering the service requirements and user needs but also the socio-economic and techno-environmental effect.

5.4. Strategy/Objectives

CiROCCO aims to develop an application-specific, low-cost, miniaturised, stand-alone and integrated multisensory electronic node that will be capable to fill-in the current technological gap for monitoring desert environment in high-density networks. The sensing node will comprise of several commercially available, low-cost and miniaturised sensors and multiple custom modules such as the power module, the intelligent control module and the interface module, to allow smooth recording of measurements from the sensors. The energy harvesting module will consist of most probably a photovoltaic cell with high-capacity batteries for the system to last more than 2 weeks without light. The intelligent control module will consist of an AI compatible microcontroller to allow on-the-node processing at ultra-low power consumption or if needed, an FPGA/CPLD will be implemented. The packaging of the integrated node will be unique and customised to ensure the longevity of the system in harsh environments whilst allowing accurate and timely measurements. Finally, depending on the pilots' requirements, a data transmission module will be developed to transmit the data either wirelessly by WiFi, Bluetooth, Zigbee, Thread, LTE/5G or through a wired connection when feasible and if needed. To retrieve the

²¹ www.campbellsci.com/systems.

²² www.onsetcomp.com/press-release/28336/

²³ (Zrnić, et al., 2021)

²⁴ (Shaout, Yulong, Zhou, & Awad, 2014)

²⁵ (Rudati, Feriyonika, & Rahmawati, 2020)

²⁶ (Narayana, Jalihal, & Nagendra, 2022)

²⁷ <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/biome/biodesert.php#:~:text=During%20the%20day%2C%20desert%20temperatures.>

data from the edge devices, satellite communication will be provided by ASTRO through their nanosatellite network.

5.4.1. Preliminary list of CiROCCO Alliance action points and assignments:

- ❖ Commercial vehicle definition

Official confirmation from the partners is needed to enter a joint exploitation vehicle. INO will present potential modes of operation and invite partners to discuss the most viable option. A vote may be cast during the meeting and Memorandum of Understanding will be drafted in advance of the Business and Technical Cooperation Agreement / Founders Act among partners due by the end of the project. Define country/countries of operation, launch and expansion plan.

- ❖ Product definition

Define and adopt phases to build upon preliminary vision of the product design to provide maximum Product-Market fit. Define the product, the price range, target market and value propositions. Define services offered along the product and optimize bundle packages.

- ❖ Project costs

Analyse all cost categories and provide benchmark references.

- ❖ Project revenues

Identify competitor prices and conduct interviews to define desirable pricing strategy. Consider offering pre-sales through platforms such as Indiegogo. Assign purchase volumes to create a pessimistic and optimistic sales scenario.

- ❖ Investment rounds

Consider growth strategy from a start-up perspective. Submit business plan to accelerator programmes. Gather information on potential government subsidies for government sector buyers.

- ❖ Market Analysis

Conducting thorough market research to identify trends, customer preferences, and potential areas for expansion or diversification of the CiROCCO offerings.

- ❖ Financial Analysis

Conducting financial analysis to identify areas of cost reduction, revenue growth, and improved profitability.

- ❖ Business models development

Develop four business models for exploitation Renewable energy systems planning, Air quality early warning system for human health, Land use and ecosystem management, Modelling of GHGs and particles emissions.

5.4.2. CiROCCO Alliance horizontal activities

- ❖ Risk Management

Assessing potential risks associated with ongoing activities and developing strategies to mitigate these risks effectively.

- ❖ Innovation Promotion

Encouraging a culture of innovation within CiROCCO by supporting and promoting the implementation of new ideas and solutions.

5.4.3. Exploitation partnership strategy

Identify and contact potential Strategic partners, Consultancy partners and Global partners or collaboration opportunities with other organizations or stakeholders to leverage complementary strengths and resources.

Table 15: CiROCCO exploitation partnership strategy.

Strategic Partners	The Strategic Partners include Operators, Developers and major Contractors across the sectors of operation. Each Strategic Partner will have an engagement plan with CiROCCO technologies and be committed to proactively engaging with the 4 pilots.
Consultancy Partners	The Consultancy Partners include Large Industrial Actors, Analysts, Data Providers, Public Authorities and ICT SMEs. Each Consultancy Partner is committed to ensuring visibility at larger industrial events, allowing CiROCCO to better position the business for future work.
Global Partners	Global Partners are overseas likeminded organisations, which working together can mutually benefit. Each Global Partner is committed to provide an entering point for new global markets and finding local clients and partners to work with.

5.4.4. Post project assignments

- ❖ Resource Optimization

Identifying underutilized resources, such as equipment, technology, or personnel, and creating plans to maximize their productivity and cost-effectiveness.

- ❖ Process Improvement

Evaluating existing workflows and procedures to identify areas where efficiency can be improved.

- ❖ Product or Service Enhancement

Identify opportunities for improvements or additional features to increase customer satisfaction and market competitiveness.

- ❖ Project Evaluation

Evaluating ongoing and completed activities to determine their success, impact, and whether there are further opportunities for leveraging the outcomes.

- ❖ Sustainability and Social Responsibility

Integrating sustainable practices and social responsibility initiatives into the organization's strategies to create a positive impact on society and the environment.

5.5. Sales strategy and distribution channels

The sales strategy involves a targeted approach to reach potential customers and effectively communicate the value proposition of the product following the key elements listed below.

- ❖ Market Segmentation

Identify industries and applications where the need for low-cost sensing nodes in harsh environments is critical. This could include sectors such as renewable energy – solar pv, desert areas in continental Europe already subject to reforestation but prone to land degradation, air quality monitoring and infrastructure management. For more details on potential customers see paragraph 4.1.

❖ Value Proposition

Clearly articulate the benefits of the sensing nodes, emphasizing their ability to operate in harsh conditions while remaining cost-effective. For a full Value proposition see paragraph 5.4.

❖ Customization

Offer customization options to cater to specific industry needs. This may involve adapting the sensing nodes to different environmental conditions or integrating them with existing systems.

❖ Educational Marketing

Implement educational marketing campaigns to raise awareness about the benefits and applications of the sensing nodes. This will include webinars, whitepapers and case studies demonstrating successful implementations. A detailed communication and dissemination plan is submitted by each partner and the consortium is dedicated to promoting the project results in both commercial and scientific terms.

❖ Partnerships

Explore strategic partnerships with distributors, resellers or industry influencers to expand the reach of the product. Partnerships can enhance credibility and facilitate access to a wider customer base. For a detailed information on CiROCCO Partnership strategy see paragraph 5.4.3.

❖ Online Presence

Establish a strong online presence through a professional website, social media platforms and online marketplaces. Provide detailed product information, customer testimonials, and easy purchasing options.

Distribution Channels

The distribution channels should be designed to efficiently deliver the product to the target market. The following channels are preliminarily considered:

- ❖ **Direct Sales** - Utilize a direct sales team to engage with key clients and industries. This approach is particularly effective for large-scale government procurements or custom solutions.
- ❖ **Online Sales** - Leverage e-commerce platforms to enable customers to purchase sensing nodes directly through the company's website. Ensure a user-friendly interface and secure payment options.
- ❖ **Distributors and Resellers** - Form partnerships with distributors and resellers who specialize in the target industries. Distributors can handle large volumes, while resellers may focus on specific geographical regions.
- ❖ **Trade Shows and Exhibitions** - Participate in relevant industry trade shows and exhibitions to showcase the sensing nodes to a concentrated audience. This provides an opportunity for direct interaction with potential customers and partners.
- ❖ **After-Sales Support** - Establish a robust after-sales support system to address customer inquiries, provide technical assistance and ensure customer satisfaction. This contributes to long-term customer relationships and positive word-of-mouth.

5.6. Administrative model

A Memorandum of Understanding has been drafted among the parties in order to better prepare for the commercialisation phase after the project.

5.6.1. Operating location

The operating location will be chosen based on the production facilities for assembly and calibration of the hardware which is the most demanding operation considering location. Most probably this will be Greece.

- ❖ Operating location Greece

Advantages are membership in the EU and operation according to EU laws and regulations, providing access to market in other EU countries. Geographically, the country lies in the Mediterranean which is at the crossroads for desert dust storms carrying the sand from Sahara and provides optimal transport routes towards affected regions in the area. Minimising transportation costs is a part of CiROCCO sustainability strategy and shows clear commitment to reducing the environmental impact of the CiROCCO results.

5.6.2. Organisation's structure

- ❖ Exploitation Champion role and assignments

The Exploitation Champion is a role assigned to a voluntary CiROCCO partner that focuses on maximizing the value derived from CiROCCO tangible results. This role is responsible for identifying, developing, and implementing strategies to fully utilize the commercial potential of CiROCCO assets, ultimately driving market entry and post-project commercial efforts.

- ❖ Current Exploitation Champions

NOA, ICCS, EBOS, INTRA, INO are having regular meetings to discuss the CiROCCO Alliance administrative aspects, strategy and objectives. The reports are being published in the shared folder online, maintained by ICCS.

5.6.3. Management team

The management team of the CiROCCO Alliance will comprise individuals from each of the partnering institutions. The following roles will be assigned accordingly:

- ❖ Board of Directors

CiROCCO Alliance will be overseen by a board of directors, which includes representatives from each of the partners. The board provides strategic direction, approves major decisions and ensures that the joint venture aligns with the interests of all partners.

- ❖ C-Suite

Chief Executive Officer (CEO) or Managing Director will be responsible for the overall leadership and management, execute the strategic vision set by the board and be accountable for the Alliance's performance. Chief Financial Officer (CFO) will oversee the financial matters, including budgeting, financial reporting and risk management. Chief Operations Officer (COO) will manage day-to-day operations, ensuring that the Alliance meets its operational objectives. Chief Commercial Officer (CCO) will focus on marketing strategies, sales and business development. Chief Technology Officer (CTO) or will oversee technological aspects, research and development and innovation, ensuring that the CiROCCO system remains competitive by adopting and developing relevant technologies.

- ❖ Senior management

Human Resources Director will manage personnel matters, including recruitment, training and employee relations. Legal Counsel will ensure that the Alliance operates within legal frameworks and contractual agreements in prospective regions of operation advising on legal matters, risk mitigation

and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. Project Managers will be overseeing key areas such as production, logistics and specific business units.

❖ Alliance Coordinator

A dedicated Joint Venture Coordinator may be appointed to facilitate communication between the partner companies, ensure collaboration and manage the overall relationship.

5.7. Positioning and pricing policy

5.7.1. User persona

The following User Persona is generated using AI augmented software.

❖ Demographics

Name | Dr. Aisha Patel

Age | 45

Occupation | Head of Environmental Affairs

Annual income | £80,000

Marital status | Married

Family situation | Two children, aged 12 and 15

Location | Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

❖ User Description

A seasoned environmental expert, Dr. Aisha Patel, 45, leads environmental initiatives in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. With an £80,000 annual income, she's committed to sustainable practices and seeks cost-effective meteorological solutions.

❖ Psychographics

Personal characteristics | Eco-conscious, detail-oriented, proactive

Hobbies | Gardening, hiking, attending sustainability conferences

Interests | Renewable energy, climate change mitigation

Personal aspirations | Enhance environmental sustainability in the region

Professional goals | Implement low-cost, effective meteorological monitoring

Pains | Budget constraints, data accuracy concerns

Main challenges | Integrating sensor data into existing infrastructure

Needs | Affordable, reliable meteorological sensors

Dreams | Achieve carbon-neutral status for the city of Riyadh

❖ Purchasing behaviour

Budget | Strict budget adherence for environmental projects

Purchase frequency | Biennial procurement cycles for monitoring equipment

Preferred channels | Environmental conferences, government procurement platforms

Online behaviour | Extensive research before purchasing, reliance on expert reviews

Search terms | "Low-cost desert meteorological sensors," "Sustainable weather monitoring"

Preferred brands | Proven eco-friendly sensor manufacturers

Triggers | Budget-friendly options, positive environmental impact

Barriers | Lack of transparent product information, complex installation

5.8. Branding and promotion

Branding and promotion for the CiROCCO Alliance products involves creating a unique identity that reflects the modularity of the solutions as well as collaborative efforts of partnering companies. The products should inherit the CiROCCO values or even the visual elements if appropriate, and develop suitable sub-product line logos, taglines and value propositions that incorporate elements from parent institutions, highlighting shared values and strengths.

Clear messaging and positioning are crucial, defining the Alliance's mission, vision and values. The strategy should communicate the combined expertise, resources and innovation of the partners to deliver unique value to customers.

Establishing a consistent visual identity, including colour schemes and design elements, ensures a cohesive representation. Marketing collateral, such as brochures and digital content, should showcase the Alliance's offerings and competitive advantages, featuring case studies to illustrate successful collaborations.

An online presence through a dedicated website and social media platforms helps create awareness and engage with the audience. Launch events, participation in industry conferences and a robust public relations strategy contribute to building credibility and visibility.

Collaborative marketing campaigns, including co-branded advertisements and promotions, leverage the strengths of both companies. Customer engagement initiatives, such as feedback mechanisms and loyalty programs, enhance the alliance's relationship with its audience.

Continuous monitoring and adaptation are essential for the effectiveness of branding and promotional activities. Regular analysis of key performance indicators and feedback allows informed adjustments, ensuring the alliance's brand remains relevant and resonant in the market.

6. Roll-out strategy

A well-executed rollout strategy involves careful planning, effective communication and adaptability to market dynamics. It aims to create a positive first impression, drive initial adoption and set the stage for sustained success in the market.

6.1. Market entrance and commercial launching activities

Embarking on market entry and commercial launching activities in Cyprus, Egypt, Serbia, and Spain requires a comprehensive strategy tailored to the unique characteristics of each locale. Initiating with a thorough market research phase, the goal is to gain a deep understanding of consumer behaviour, preferences and regulatory landscapes in each country.

Partnerships form a crucial aspect of this strategy, and with consortium partner networks in each country, alliances with local distributors and logistics providers can be facilitated in each market. The support of pilot leaders is crucial in this regard, as their positive user experience is the corner stone of a resilient distribution network, ensuring the future widespread availability of the product and services. Simultaneously, cultural sensitivity is prioritised, necessitating the tailoring of marketing messages and materials to align seamlessly with the cultural nuances of Cyprus, Egypt, Serbia and Spain. Translation of marketing materials and system presentations into the local language is undertaken, adopting Greek for Cyprus, Arabic for Egypt, Serbian for Serbia and Spanish for Spain.

In the post project commercial phase, strategic launch events or campaigns will be orchestrated in each country to create awareness and maximise visibility. Collaborations with local media outlets and influencers will further enhance the reach and impact of these initiatives. Adherence to local regulatory requirements is of importance, guiding the process to obtain necessary certifications for compliance with product or service standards.

Digital marketing assumes a prominent role in the marketing mix, leveraging online channels such as social media, local websites and e-commerce platforms to reach a broader audience. The high mobile penetration in Egypt prompts the inclusion of mobile marketing strategies to maximise outreach. For B2B offerings, engagement with local businesses is prioritised through networking events, conferences and direct outreach. Additionally, proactive efforts in government relations aim to establish positive relationships with relevant regulatory and management bodies in each country.

The provision of customer support in the local language becomes imperative, necessitating the establishment of local customer service channels to address queries effectively. Throughout these initiatives, continuous monitoring of performance metrics, market dynamics and customer feedback will be prioritised. This iterative approach ensures adaptability, allowing for strategic adjustments based on real-time insights.

6.2. Funding opportunities

Securing funding for a joint venture in the context of real-time data collection and analysis, necessitates a strategic exploration of various funding avenues available in the EU. The primary source of support lies in government grants and funding programmes given the nature of the project.

Primarily, it is to be expected that some of the technical partners will continue to work on their solutions through seeking funding in future similar Horizon Europe calls and other European and national innovation support programmes.

Considering the strong cooperation with governmental institutions already established in the consortium, public-private partnerships emerge as a strategic option, involving collaboration with public entities or private companies with a vested interest in environmental monitoring. Such partnerships can not only bring in funding but also provide access to valuable resources and expertise.

Venture capital and angel investors represent another promising funding source. Investors with an interest in technology and environmental solutions may be attracted to a joint venture focused on in-situ monitoring, particularly if it demonstrates innovation, scalability and potential for positive environmental impact.

Other avenues include exploring crowdfunding platforms to engage a broader audience and pursuing collaborations with corporations that share an interest in environmental sustainability or data-driven solutions.

Ultimately, the success of securing funding relies on developing a compelling business case. Clearly articulating the value proposition of the in-situ monitoring technology, demonstrating its potential impact and showcasing a well-defined path to commercialisation are crucial elements that can attract financial support from diverse sources. Staying informed about upcoming opportunities and fostering industry connections further enhances the CiROCCO Alliance's prospects for securing the necessary funding.

6.3. Risk analysis and Mitigation measures

❖ Market Risks

Fluctuations in market demand, changing consumer preferences and economic uncertainties may impact the market position. Mitigation: Conduct regular market research, maintain flexibility in production and marketing strategies and diversify offerings to adapt to changing market conditions.

❖ Operational Risks

Operational disruptions, supply chain issues and technological failures can hinder the smooth functioning of the Alliance. Mitigation: Develop a robust supply chain management system, implement contingency plans for potential disruptions and invest in technology resilience measures.

❖ Financial Risks

Economic downturns, unexpected costs or funding challenges are typical examples of financial risks. Mitigation: Maintain a financial buffer, conduct thorough financial planning and explore diverse funding sources. Implement stringent financial controls and monitoring.

❖ Legal and Regulatory Risks

Changes in regulations, legal disputes or compliance issues may affect the operations. Mitigation: Stay informed about legal and regulatory developments, engage legal experts for compliance and establish transparent communication channels with regulatory authorities.

❖ Cultural and Communication Risks

Cultural differences and communication breakdowns between partners may lead to misunderstandings or conflicts. Mitigation: Implement cross-cultural training, establish effective communication protocols and foster a collaborative culture to mitigate misunderstandings and build strong working relationships.

❖ Technology Risks

Dependence on technology for operations exposes the joint venture to cybersecurity threats, data breaches or technological obsolescence. Mitigation: Invest in robust cybersecurity measures, conduct

regular technology assessments and stay updated on emerging technologies. Develop contingency plans for technology failures.

❖ Intellectual Property Risks

Potential disputes over intellectual property rights or concerns about the protection of proprietary information. Mitigation: Clearly define intellectual property rights in the CiROCCO Alliance business and technical cooperation agreement, implement strict confidentiality measures and conduct regular audits to ensure compliance.

❖ Partnership Risks

Differences in strategic goals, management styles or unforeseen conflicts between the partners may impact the Alliance. Mitigation: Establish a comprehensive CiROCCO Alliance business and technical cooperation agreement outlining roles, responsibilities and dispute resolution mechanisms. Foster open communication and maintain a collaborative approach to problem-solving.

❖ Political and Geopolitical Risks:

Political instability, changes in government policies or geopolitical tensions may affect the operations, especially because the planned expansion includes multiple countries. Mitigation: Stay informed about political developments, diversify operations across stable regions and conduct thorough risk assessments before entering new markets.

❖ Exit Strategy Risks

Lack of a well-defined exit strategy may pose challenges if partners wish to terminate the joint venture. Mitigation: Develop a clear exit strategy in the CiROCCO Alliance business and technical cooperation agreement, outlining conditions and processes for termination. Regularly review and update the exit plan as needed.

6.3.1. Monitoring and assessment

Regular monitoring, periodic risk assessments and proactive mitigation measures are essential to ensure the long-term success and sustainability of the CiROCCO Alliance. All the assignments, methodology definition and the implementation process will be defined in mutual agreement among the Alliance partners. A timely implementation taking into account the market challenges, industry differences and the cultural practices in different regions will ensure that the CiROCCO Alliance remains well-prepared to navigate uncertainties and capitalize on opportunities.

7. Conclusion and outlook

This document serves as a comprehensive guideline delineating both the joint and individual exploitation plans of the partners involved in the CiROCCO system. It intricately details the strategic approach towards commercialising the CiROCCO system and lays the foundation for the establishment of the post-project CiROCCO Alliance. The meticulous planning and coordination embedded within these exploitation plans are integral to the joint venture's success.

The commercial strategy outlined herein is specifically tailored for the CiROCCO system, taking into account the unique features and capabilities it offers in the Earth Observation (EO) sector. As the document reflects, the market outlook for the EO sector appears highly promising, with an optimistic trajectory poised for growth. The joint commitment of the partners to actively engage in commercialisation activities not only underscores their collective confidence in the CiROCCO system but also serves as a robust indicator of the Alliance's potential for future success.

Moreover, the document signifies a forward-looking approach, anticipating the sustained commercial viability of the CiROCCO Alliance beyond the project's conclusion. The establishment of the CiROCCO Alliance post-project is a strategic move, demonstrating a commitment to the long-term viability of the joint venture and the continuation of collaborative efforts.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled. The four business services were described as business models using the business model canvas tool, with two of the models presented to the local stakeholders during the stakeholders' workshops in Cyprus and Serbia. The feedback was valuable, providing insights into the inclination of the participants towards commercial value as well as providing overall feedback on the value proposition and better definition of the customer channels and approach. The remaining two workshops in Egypt and Spain will complement the assessment and provide market specific information upon realization (most probably to be realized by the end of February 2024).

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Annex 1: Datasets Exploitation summary

Table 16: Exploitation summary for datasets created during CiROCCO.

DATASET	FORMAT	PARTNER	STORAGE	OPEN/ PROTECTED	EXPLOITATION MODE
Solar energy monitoring and forecasting	netcdf/ mat/csv	NOA (SOLEA)	cloud	Open source during the project	Commercial provision. Support the distributed solar plants for production management, energy market operations optimization, maintenance efficient planning and early warning, energy security.
WRF -DUST	netCDF	NOA (REACT)	CiROCCO system	open	Provide Information about the prevailing air quality
WRF-DUST-Assimilated	netCDF	NOA (REACT)	CiROCCO system	open	Provide improved quality Information about the prevailing air quality
Data and metadata for the parametrization and results for the CiROCCO sensor-systems, with emphasis on PM measurements	csv	IERSD (APCG)	Cloud/Zenodo	Open source after the project	Will support the research and sensor community to guide QAQC processes applied to commercial and under-development systems
Desert Dust Storm (DDS) Events Data	.csv	UCY	UCY	Open Source	The DDS Events Data can be used to better forecast future dust storms, helping to protect and prepare communities. End users benefit from improved forecasting accuracy and subsequent early warning alerts.
Early Warning System User Engagement Data	.xlsx	UCY	UCY	Open Source	User engagement data can be analysed to identify areas for improvement in the early warning system, enhancing the user experience and ensuring maximum impact. End users benefit from a system that is constantly improved and updated based on user feedback.

DATASET	FORMAT	PARTNER	STORAGE	OPEN/ PROTECTED	EXPLOITATION MODE
Sensors' readings	TBD	EBOS	CiROCCO data storage space	Open Source	EBOS does not plan to exploit the datasets at this stage
Land use / Land cover map	GeoTIFF	INO	VŠUME server, Data integration and management platform	Opensource	further research/development
Ecological vulnerability map	GEOTiff	INO	VŠUME server	Protected	further research/development, internal use
Long term ecological management study	PDF	INO	Zenodo	Opensource	further research/development
Short term wild fire risk map	GEOTiff	INO	VŠUME server, StreamHandler Platform	Opensource	Public use, comercial, further research
Short term drought risk map	GEOTiff	INO	VŠUME server, StreamHandler Platform	Opensource	Public use, comercial, further research
Database Inventory of Meteorological and Air Quality Data, monitoring and alerting tools and models for historical, current and future analysis of DDS exposure	.csv	UCY: Development and design MOL: Data provider, design	ICCS	Open Access	Future application in other Municipalities and Communities (inform the public, especially the vulnerable population groups for the air quality of their region). Measurements of the Air Quality Monitoring Network will be enriched at the local level.

Annex 2: Individual Exploitation Plan Template

The following template was sent out to all partners by email.

[PARTNER NAME]	+ X EMPLOYEES
Brief intro to your organization and short analysis of the market in which your organization is currently operating	
[100 words max]	
Expected Impact	
Please answer the following. How will CiROCCO support:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Evolution of your organization, and/ or expansion to new sectors of interest. > Growth and development of your products and services. > Reaching out to more/ new customers. 	

IP Rights

CiROCCO Partner	Background IPR / Project Contribution	Business Opportunity/ foreground

DATASETS

Dataset	Format	Responsible partner	Where the data will be stored	Opensource/ Protected	Exploitation Mode
[name of dataset]	[type of file format]	[partner]	[e.g., on which server or data archive]	[describe]	[desired exploitation of the dataset, how do the end users benefit]

PUBLICATIONS

[please check all the boxes that apply to your organisation's plans and possible contribution]

Peer reviewed articles	<input type="checkbox"/>
Research assessment/study	<input type="checkbox"/>
Poster	<input type="checkbox"/>
Product brochures	<input type="checkbox"/>

Blog posts	<input type="checkbox"/>
Project brochures/leaflets	<input type="checkbox"/>
Infographics	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other diss&comm material	<input type="checkbox"/>

Annex 3: DRAFT CiROCCO Memorandum of Understanding – sample pages

Memorandum of understanding

for the establishment of

CiROCCO Alliance

Between

CiROCCO Coordinator, **Institute of Communication and Computer Science (ICCS)**

and

CiROCCO Partner, **Ethniko Asteroskopeio Athinon (NOA)**

and

CiROCCO Partner, **eBOS Technologies Limited (EBOS)**

and

CiROCCO Partner, **Netcompany-Intrasoft SA (INTRA)**

and

CiROCCO Partner, **InoSens doo Novi Sad (INO)**

and

CiROCCO Partner, **University of Cyprus (UCY)**

DD MM YYYY

Funded by
the European Union

I PURPOSE & SCOPE

This MOU demonstrates the intention of all partners to establish a joint venture “CiROCCO Alliance” and aims to identify the roles and responsibilities of each party as they relate to CiROCCO commercialisation within the Alliance. Considering these legal and institutional relations, the successful commercialisation of the CiROCCO System requires partnership between the six (6) signatory institutions, which this MoU shall facilitate. The parties therefore have entered this MoU for the purpose of the commercialisation journey of the CiROCCO System.

The Alliance intends to approach target customers such as ESA, Weather Stations Operators & Manufacturers, Environmental Agencies and Ministries, Scientific Earth Observation Bodies, RES Manufacturers and Installers, Meteorological Services, other Public Bodies and relevant stakeholders in the European Union and Candidate Countries as well as globally.

II RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS OF THE PARTIES

All parties will ensure that activities are conducted in compliance with all applicable EU laws and good business practice. Each organization has a right to maintain its own identity in providing services. Each party is an independent contractor to the other. Each organization will also maintain a brand partnership defined as an alliance to work together to create marketing synergy.

III TERM

CiROCCO commercialisation is expected to start immediately after the project is completed. The term of this agreement is the period within which the responsibilities of this agreement shall be performed. This term commences by the date of signing of all parties and terminates when CiROCCO Alliance is officially established and registered, as it will be replaced by the CiROCCO Alliance founding document.

IV ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF PARTNERS

All parties agree to share the initial set up costs related to the administration and day-to-day operations of the Alliance. All parties agree to promote and advertise the CiROCCO system through their networks to support sales. Individual parties take responsibility for maintenance, development and technical support of the CiROCCO system components belonging to their IPR share. In the case of shared IPR, responsibilities are equally shared to reflect the initial arrangement.

Individual parties’ roles and responsibilities are outlined as follows:

1. ICCS will provide required maintenance and technical support related to the

following components of the CiROCCO System:

- a. Low-cost sensing nodes. For the purposes of this MoU, low-cost sensing nodes are defined as a combination of hardware and software tools as developed and deployed on CiROCCO pilot sites to gather in-situ monitoring data, specifically designed to operate stand alone and in harsh environments.
2. NOA will provide required maintenance and technical support related to the following components of the CiROCCO System:
 - a. Data fusion service between high- and low-end sensors
 - b. Data fusion between EO and in-situ measurements
 - c. Renewable energy systems planning
3. EBOS will provide required maintenance and technical support related to the following components of the CiROCCO System:
 - a. Low-cost sensing nodes design blueprints. For the purposes of this MoU, low-cost sensing nodes are defined as a combination of hardware and software tools as developed and deployed on CiROCCO pilot sites to gather in-situ monitoring data, specifically designed to operate stand alone and in harsh environments.
4. INTRA will provide required maintenance and technical support related to the following components of the CiROCCO System:
 - a. **Sample text here.** For the purposes of this MoU, **sample text here.**
 - b. **Sample text here.** For the purposes of this MoU, **sample text here.**
5. INO will provide business and customer support, including:
 - a. Initial cost structure for first year of Alliance operation, Founder Act draft and Pitch deck presentation.
 - b. Business planning, marketing and sales.
 - c. Customer relationship management and after sales support.
6. UCY will provide required maintenance and technical support related to the following components of the CiROCCO System:
 - a. **Sample text here.** For the purposes of this MoU, **sample text here.**
 - b. **Sample text here.** For the purposes of this MoU, **sample text here.**

V Intellectual Property Rights

Background and foreground IPR of the parties is assessed based on individual

IP name	Description	Type	Owner	Rights to use the foreground
Electronic Sensing System	The stand-alone electronic system that will accommodate the several sensors, obtain data from them and transmit them to the main platform	Hardware	EBOS	Licencing
Ecological management model	Ecological management model based on EO products, field surveys of changes in land degradation and evaluation of risk factors	Software/platform implementation of conceptual model	INO	Licencing
Data Inventory	Inventory of Meteorological and Air Quality Data, monitoring and alerting tools and models for historical, current and future analysis of DDS exposure	Database	UCY, DIMOS	Open Access
Inventory of tools and models	Inventory of monitoring and alerting tools and models for DDS exposure	Scientific study	UCY	Open Access
Air quality early warning system for human health				
Mitigation and Adaption measures	Design a series of mitigation and adaptation measures related to Desert Dust Storms, in a congested urban environment	Scientific study	DIMOS	Open Access
Gateway	Software development to gather all	Software	ICCS	Open Access

Annex 4: Business model canvas template

Business Model Canvas		Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
		Solution Name	Name1, Name2, ...	DD/MM/YYYY	X.Y
Key Partners <p>For whom are we creating value? Who are our most important customers? Is our customer base a Mass Market, Niche Market, Segmented, Diversified, Multi-sided Platform</p>					
	Key Resources <p>Through which Channels do our Customer Segments want to be reached? How are we reaching them now? How are our Channels integrated? Which ones work best? Which ones are most cost-efficient? How are we integrating them with customer routines?</p>				
Cost Structure <p>For what value are our customers really willing to pay? For what do they currently pay? How are they currently paying? How would they prefer to pay? How much does each Revenue Stream contribute to overall revenues?</p> <p>TYPES: Asset sale, Usage fee, Subscription Fees, Lending/Renting/Leasing, Licensing, Brokerage fees, Advertising</p> <p>FIXED PRICING: List Price, Product feature dependent, Customer segment dependent, Volume dependent</p> <p>DYNAMIC PRICING: Negotiation (bargaining), Yield Management, Real-time-Market</p>					

Annex 5: Exploitation survey results Cyprus

What kind of a system is it?

Value proposition

Do you know of any example related to Desert Dust Storms?

Value proposition

How may you benefit from a service that notifies you of a Desert Dust Storm in advance?
5 responses

Stay home to avoid any health issues if vulnerable	Reduce personal activities	Health, visibility,
To schedule the outside work of a company's employees	Take preventative measures. Notify citizens on time.	

Which geographical region will be under the heaviest influence from DDS over the next 5 years?
9 responses

I dont know	Mediterranean	Mediterranean region
Middle east	Middle east and broader area including Cyprus	North Africa, south Mediterranean
Cyprus	Mediterranean region	North Africa

Mentimeter

Are there any large cities in the area?
5 responses

Cairo	Cairo	Cairo, Nicosia, Athens
Tel aviv	Cairo	

2 5

Mentimeter

Do you foresee any particular business risk in approaching this market?
6 responses

Aviation	Goverments developing their own systems	Tourism image
No	Any business during force alarm!!!	Hard to penetrate particular "market" in Greece and win a government contract

2 6

Revenue streams

Would you pay for the on-demand text communication with meteorologists?

Mentimeter

3 6

Revenue streams

How would you rate membership rewards, if subscribed?

Mentimeter

6

Mentimeter

How would you describe the replicability/upscaling of the Air Quality Early Warning System for Human Health service in the five years post-project?

Option	Description	Votes
High	High – CiROCCO system can go global with this business service	1
Moderate	Moderate – CiROCCO system would need additional effort and funds to expand to other markets	8
Low	Low – CiROCCO system is a tailored solution, we should go for few, but large contracts	0

2 9

Mentimeter

Can you suggest a strategic partner for this business service?

4 responses

- Industry partners (sensor and air cleaner manufacturers)
- Health services, Insurance
- Local authorities
- EMRO WHO

3

Mentimeter

Can you suggest a Consultancy partner for this business service?
1 response

Insurance sector

1

A Mentimeter poll slide with a background image of sand dunes. The question is "Can you suggest a Consultancy partner for this business service?" and it shows "1 response". A single response box contains the text "Insurance sector". There is a thumbs up icon and a person icon with the number "1" next to it.

Mentimeter

Can you suggest a Global partner for this business service?
3 responses

? European Environmental Agency EMRO WHO

3 3

A Mentimeter poll slide with a background image of sand dunes. The question is "Can you suggest a Global partner for this business service?" and it shows "3 responses". Three response boxes are visible: the first contains "?", the second contains "European Environmental Agency", and the third contains "EMRO WHO". There are two thumbs up icons and two person icons, each with the number "3" next to it.

Mentimeter

If you had an app on your phone called Air Quality Early Warning System for Human Health, how would you call it?
8 responses

DustIN	DustIt	Dust EWS
BreathClean	LongLife! 😊	Dust in my area.
AirQ app	Duster	

8

Annex 6: Exploitation survey results Serbia

Mentimeter

If yes, can you tell us who the service provider is?

Government and statups	National parks	Greek government	RHMZS
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Mentimeter

What kind of a system is it?

System Type	Count
Internally developed system	2
Web based app	0
Combo of above	5
Other	1

Value proposition

Mentimeter

How do you propose we reach our government customers most effectively?

Political connections	in-person product presentations	Political connections	Demo days
Social media			

1 5

Mentimeter

Do you know of any support tool related to wildfire prevention?

Response	Count
Yes	6
No	4

2 10

Value proposition

Mentimeter

If yes, could you tell us more about the service of the provider?

Video surveillance of Vojvodinasume	Real-time mapa koja prikazuje aktivne požare na teritoriji RS	Within Landsense project. Developed by GeoVille	It's a prevention system which warns of high fire risk (based on temperature, wind intensity etc)
Senzori za dim	Private market companies	Fire risk warning	

1 6

Mentimeter

How may you benefit from a service that notifies you of a wildfire occurrence probability?

Avoid high risk areas	Brza reakcija	Avoiding high risk areas	Avoiding personal and material damage
Preventivno delovanje	avoid high risk activities	Prevent some activities	

1 5

How important for sustainable ecosystem management are these processes?

Value proposition

How may you benefit from sustainable ecosystem management?

Value proposition

Mentimeter

Are there any large forest ecosystems in your area?

no	Yes	Yes	Yes
Da	Yes	Yes	Yes

👍 👤

Mentimeter

Are there any large forest ecosystems in your area?

Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Koviljski rit	Yes		

👍 👤

Mentimeter

How would you describe the replicability/upscaling of the Land Use and Ecosystems Management service in the five years post-project?

Replicability/upscale description	Votes
High – CiROCCO system can go global with this business service	6
Moderate – CiROCCO system would need additional effort and funds to expand to other markets	5
Low – CiROCCO system is a tailored solution, we should go for few, but large contracts	0

3 11

Mentimeter

Can you suggest a strategic partner for this business service?

RHMZ	Ministarstvo zivotne sredine	SEPA	Agrncija za zivotnu sredinu
Ministarstvo poljoprivrede	(National or regional) Operational centers for disaster management	Dvoper	

3

Mentimeter

Can you suggest a Consultancy partner for this business service?

Zelena Stolica na republičkom nivou, ali i pokrajinska	Scientific institute and Faculties	national forestry agency	ECMWF / COPERNICUS
Private institutes	Institut za bioloska ispitivanja- Beograd	Biosence	

6

Mentimeter

Can you suggest a Global partner for this business service?

EEA	WHO	NASA / ESA	Eea
WMO	Ecomanagement		

3

Mentimeter

If you had an app on your computer called Land Use and Ecosystem Management Decision support system, how would you call it?

No	Ecomanagement	Land	LUEMDSS
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👍 👤